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D2.7 – Final release of demonstration workflows

WP2: Convergence of HPC/HPDA and Improved Usability

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the final release of demonstration workflows for the BioExcel-2 project, including a wrap-up of all the work done for the BioBB library, its associated workflows, and a final analysis of the milestones achieved from the initial roadmap.

The current release of the BioExcel Building Blocks library is presented in the first section, underlining the FAIR development process followed, including the automatic generation of the BioBB adapters from the Python documentation. The current available modules (categories) in the library are listed. Finally, the landing website and its different sections are briefly described.

The second section enumerates the final collection of demonstration workflows, with a brief description of what each workflow does, the tools used, and links to the source code and documentation. The library versatility, validated with the collection of demonstration workflows, is explained, and links to the different workflow flavours are presented in a summary table.

The power of the pre-exascale demonstration workflows is presented in the fourth section, with examples of workflows successfully applied to real scientific projects (success stories).

The following section focuses on the broad range of possibilities to find and execute BioExcel workflows, from local or HPC installations, to web-based interfaces.

Visibility and uptake is discussed in the sixth section, listing a number of training events, webinars and scientific drafts with the presence of the library and the demonstration workflows.

The final section revisits the proposed roadmap for the WP2, analysing the status of the intended milestones at the end of the project, with comments on the progress, potential issues and redefined tasks.

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1 Introduction

The BioExcel Centre of Excellence for Computational Biomolecular Research was established as an European H2020 project in the year 2015. One of the goals of the project was to increase the usability of our tools by designing, deploying and making available solution-oriented biomolecular workflows. An initial exploratory phase revealed a number of important issues to tackle for this particular task: a lack of interoperability between biomolecular tools, lack of standards in data formats and associated metadata, and a great difficulty in reproducing and/or reusing workflows, mainly due to the software dependencies.

Taking all these points into account, the project decided to work on the design of a new library, mainly focused on increasing our tools interoperability, but also trying to improve reproducibility, a very important topic for the whole science field. The new library was called BioExcel Building Blocks (BioBB) [1].

Today, almost seven years later, the library is a central piece of the BioExcel workflows, with more than 25 tools wrapped and a total of 150 available building blocks. Workflows built using the library are reproducible thanks to the Conda packaging system used. The available BioBB BioConda packages accumulate more than 115,000 downloads as of today (June 2022) (<https://anaconda.org/search?q=biobb>). A collection of demonstration workflows have been developed and made available using Jupyter Notebooks, and have been successfully used in training events. The combination of the BioBB library with the PyCOMPSs workflow manager [2] has produced a set of HPC-focused workflows, able to efficiently use thousands of supercomputer cores; and proved its power in a number of ambitious scientific projects.

The library and its associated workflows are openly accessible to the scientific community through a variety of on-line resources. Source code is available from the GitHub repositories. Documentation is compiled with Readthedocs. Workflows can be downloaded from the WorkflowsHub repository [3] and can be executed in the BioExcel myBinder infrastructure, a cloud infrastructure deploying Jupyter Notebooks. A central website is gathering together all the information, links and tutorials:

<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb>

This document brings together all the work done in the BioExcel-2 period with the BioBB library and its associated workflows, highlighting the most important achievements, and revisiting the roadmap proposed at the beginning of the project.

2 BioExcel Building Blocks library (BioBB)

The BioExcel Building Blocks library (BioBB) is a collection of Python wrappers on top of biomolecular simulation tools, with particular focus on tools interoperability [1]. Designed during the first BioExcel period (2016-2018), the library eases the process of building complex workflows which use different biomolecular simulation tools together, a common activity in the field. The library adds an interoperability layer making all the integrated tools compatible with each other, using a uniform syntax.

Additionally and thanks to the packaging systems used (Conda packages [4], containers [5]), it provides an additional level of reusability and reproducibility. It was designed to be workflow-manager and infrastructure agnostic, with the possibility to be used with different available workflow managers and hardware architectures, varying from HPC supercomputers to Cloud infrastructures, and from HPC-based workflow managers (e.g. PyCOMPSs [2]) to Drag & Drop Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs) (e.g. Galaxy [6, 7], KNIME [8]). The whole software development process follows the set of ELIXIR-compliant FAIR principles for research software [9]. Whereas the first BioExcel period was dedicated to the definition and designing process, the second period (2019-2022) has established the library as a mature technology.

An extended summary of the library design process was presented in the final WP2 deliverable (D2.4) of the BioExcel-1 period (doi:[10.5281/zenodo.3236256](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3236256)), which constituted the library version v1.0. Deliverable D2.2 of the BioExcel-2 period (doi:[10.5281/zenodo.4605207](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4605207)) presented the software development process and the state of the library in the 2019.4 release (v2.0). The following sections of this deliverable present the BioBB ecosystem at the end of the BioExcel-2 project, summarising the new added features and main achievements of these last years, included in the last BioBB release 2022.2 (v.3.8.0).

2.1 BioBB development

The software development process of the BioBB library was designed to follow the set of FAIR principles for research software [9]. For that, all the building blocks source code, organized in categories/modules (see next section) is available through the [BioExcel GitHub repository](#) (see Table 1). Besides, a Conda package and a Docker/Singularity container are created for each category. Finally, the building blocks are comprehensively documented using Readthedocs.

Following the steps of the main software codes in BioExcel, 4 main releases were planned per year, i.e. one every 3 months. Release notes are published in the BioBB web site (<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/availability/release-notes>, see section 2.5). The current release is the 2022.1 (v.3.7, March 2022).

Development feedback from our users is collected through standard GitHub issues. An exclusive BioExcel forum (ask.bioexcel.eu) is also available for our users, providing discussion space for each of the BioExcel tools, as well as for the

BioExcel training events as they are run (e.g. [BioExcel Summer School 2021](#)). A dedicated page of the BioBB website organises the available resources according to the BioBB packages, workflows or side projects (<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/contact>, see section 2.5).

2.2 BioBB modules

The BioBB library building blocks are divided into categories, according to the functionality behind the software wrapped (see Table 1). The BioBB library at the end of the BioExcel-1 period (v1.0) included 6 categories:

- [biobb common](#): base package required to use the BioBB library.
- [biobb io](#): collection to fetch data from biological databases.
- [biobb model](#): collection to check and model 3D structures.
- [biobb md](#): collection to perform Molecular Dynamics simulations using the GROMACS BioExcel core application.
- [biobb analysis](#): collection to perform analysis of MD simulations.

BioExcel-2 D2.2 presented the new categories included during the first year of the BioExcel-2 period (v2.0, 2019.1), developed mainly for the BioExcel-2 defined use cases:

- [biobb pmx](#): collection to perform free energy calculations using the pmx BioExcel key application.
- [biobb structure utils](#): collection to extract information from a PDB structure file.
- [biobb chemistry](#): collection to perform cheminformatics analyses and format conversions.

BioExcel-2 D2.4 (doi:[10.5281/zenodo.4916029](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4916029)) presented a new category focused on Machine Learning and included in the BioBB v3.0, 2020.2:

- [biobb ml](#): collection to perform Machine Learning (ML) tasks, including classification, regression, clustering, neural networks and dimensionality reduction.

Finally, the current release (v.3.7, 2022.1) comprises 14 different categories, including 4 newly developed ones:

- [biobb amber](#): collection to perform MD simulations using the AMBER MD package.
- [biobb cmip](#): collection to perform classical molecular interaction potential calculation on macromolecular structures.
- [biobb dna](#): collection to perform nucleic acids specific analysis on DNA structures or MD trajectories.
- [biobb remote](#): a special collection to remotely connect GUIs such as Jupyter Notebooks or web-based interfaces to HPC supercomputers.

<i>BioBB Module</i>	<i>Module Brief Description</i>	<i>GitHub</i>	<i>ReadTheDocs</i>	<i>Conda</i>	<i>Docker</i>
<i>biobb_amber</i>	BioBB category for AMBER MD package, allowing setup and simulation of atomistic MD simulations using AMBER MD package and its associated AMBER tools				
<i>biobb_analysis</i>	BioBB module collection to perform analysis of molecular dynamics simulations				
<i>biobb_chemistry</i>	BioBB module collection to perform chemistry over molecular dynamics simulations				
<i>biobb_cmip</i>	BioBB module collection to compute classical molecular interaction potentials				
<i>biobb_common</i>	BioBB base package required to use the rest of the modules				
<i>biobb_dna</i>	BioBB module package composed of different analyses for nucleic acid trajectories				
<i>biobb_io</i>	BioBB module collection to fetch data to be consumed by the rest of the Biobb building blocks				
<i>biobb_md</i>	BioBB module collection to perform molecular dynamics simulations with GROMACS MD package				
<i>biobb_ml</i>	BioBB module collection to perform machine learning predictions				
<i>biobb_model</i>	BioBB module collection to check and model 3d structures, create mutations or reconstruct missing atoms				
<i>biobb_pmx</i>	BioBB module collection to perform PMX executions				
<i>biobb_remote</i>	BioBB module collection to remotely connect GUIs to HPC supercomputers		-		
<i>biobb_structure_utils</i>	BioBB module collection to modify or extract information from a PDB structure file				
<i>biobb_vs</i>	BioBB module collection to perform virtual screening studies				

Table.1 .-List of currently available BioBB modules (Release 2022.1).
<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/documentation/source>

2.3 BioBB adapters & ecosystem

The BioBB library is formed by three different layers (Fig.1a). From inner to outer: 1) the *tool execution layer*, where the original tool is run; 2) the (*Python*) *compatibility layer*, which provides tool interoperability by means of a unified interface for input, output and configuration parameters, internally converted to a compatible tool command line; and 3) the *adaptor layer*, adding the ability to use the building blocks in different workflow managers or execution engines. Thanks to this external layer, the BioBB library has been successfully integrated in execution tools as diverse as Galaxy web-based GUI ([Galaxy xml nodes](#)), HPC-focused PyCOMPSs workflow manager ([PyCOMPSs adapters](#)), CWL workflows ([CWL specifications](#)) and REST API endpoints ([REST API endpoints](#)).

Notably, the different adapter layers are automatically spawned from the BioBB source code documentation (Python docstrings), thanks to an integrative schema generated after exploring several execution tools. This documentation is then transformed to a JSON schema, which, in turn, is converted to the different adapters (Fig. 1b). Particularly interesting is the automatic creation of the BioBB

REST API endpoints collection (<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb-api/>, see also section 2.4) for each of the BioBB building blocks, including sample files allowing automatic weekly autotests.

c)

```

class Pdb4amberRun(BiobbObject):
    """
    | biobb_amber.pdb4amber.pdb4amber_run Pdb4amberRun
    | Wrapper of the `AmberTools` (AMBER MD Package) `pdb4amber` tool <https://ambermd.org/AmberTools.php>`_` module.
    | Analyse PDB files and clean them for further usage, especially with the LEaP programs of Amber, using `pdb4amber` tool from
    | the AmberTools MD package.
    |
    | Args:
    |     input_pdb_path (str): Input 3D structure PDB file. File type: input. `Sample file <https://github.com/bioexcel
    | /biobb_amber/raw/master/biobb_amber/test/data/pdb4amber/laki_fixed.pdb>`_. Accepted formats: pdb (edam:format_1476).
    |     output_pdb_path (str): Output 3D structure PDB file. File type: output. `Sample file <https://github.com/bioexcel
    | /biobb_amber/raw/master/biobb_amber/test/reference/pdb4amber/structure.pdb4amber.pdb>`_. Accepted formats: pdb
    | (edam:format_1476).
    |     properties (dict - Python dictionary object containing the tool parameters, not input/output files):
    |         * **remove_hydrogens** (*bool*) - (False) Remove hydrogen atoms from the PDB file.
    |         * **remove_waters** (*bool*) - (False) Remove water molecules from the PDB file.
    |         * **constant_ph** (*bool*) - (False) Rename ionizable residues e.g. GLU,ASP,HIS for constant pH simulation.
    |         * **remove_tmp** (*bool*) - (True) [WF property] Remove temporal files.
    |         * **restart** (*bool*) - (False) [WF property] Do not execute if output files exist.
    |
    | Examples:
    | This is a use example of how to use the building block from Python::
    |
    |     from biobb_amber.pdb4amber.pdb4amber_run import pdb4amber_run
    |     prop = {
    |         'remove_tmp': True
    |     }
    |     pdb4amber_run(input_pdb_path='/path/to/structure.pdb',
    |                   output_pdb_path='/path/to/newStructure.pdb',
    |                   properties=prop)
    |
    | Info:
    | * wrapped_software:
    |   * name: AmberTools `pdb4amber`
    |   * version: >20.9
    |   * license: LGPL 2.1
    | * ontology:
    |   * name: EDAM
    |   * schema: http://edamontology.org/EDAM.owl
    """

```

Fig.1 - a) BioExcel building blocks three-layer architecture. b) Automatic generation of adapters and REST API endpoints from the BioBB source code (Python docstrings). c) Example of building block documentation (Python docstring), used for the automatic generation of the different adapters (Building Block Pdb4Amber, from the biobb_amber module).

Information included in the building blocks documentation is a minimum set of metadata needed for the execution tools to integrate them. Typically, this information comprises name, format, description and sample files (when possible) of input/output files, and name, format and default values for

additional parameters. Additionally, information about the library and wrapped tool versions is always important for provenance. Figure 1c gives an example of documentation for the *Pdb4Amber* building block included in the *biobb_amber* module.

Thanks to this documentation schema and the automatic procedure presented, new execution possibilities might be explored in the near future (e.g. Nextflow data-driven computational pipeline [10]).

The outcome of this collection of automatically generated BioBB adapters is an entire ecosystem surrounding the main building blocks source code, widening the usability and visibility of the library (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2.- BioBB side projects: HPC workflows, CWL workflows, Drag & Drop GUIs (Galaxy, KNIME), Web-based GUI (BioBB-Wfs) and REST API programmatic access (BioBB-API).

2.4 BioBB landing page

As seen in the previous sections, the BioBB library has evolved into a complex ecosystem, including a collection of modules, demonstration workflows (in different flavours), documentation, Conda packages and containers. The BioBB landing page (<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/>) tries to centralize and organize all the information, giving an ordered access to all the information scattered in different sites (GitHub, Readthedocs, Anaconda, quay.io, WorkflowHub, Galaxy-ES). We describe the main layout sections below:

The collection of BioBB modules, with links to the corresponding source code, documentation, Conda packages and containers, can be found in the *Source and Docs* section of the website (Fig. 3a):

<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/documentation/source>

The collection of demonstration workflows, with links to the corresponding WorkflowHub entries for the different workflow flavours, source code, tutorial, documentation and live environments with the possibility to execute the workflow (Fig. 3b), can be found in the *Workflows* section of the website:

<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/workflows>

The different possibilities available to directly build and/or run BioBB workflows without the need of any local installation (Galaxy, BioBB-Wfs website, BioBB-API) can be found in:

<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/availability/launch>

The different ways to install the BioBB library modules and the associated demonstration workflows can be found in:

<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/availability/download>

Tutorials on how to install Anaconda packaging software, the only software required to easily build and execute workflows with the BioBB library, for different Operating Systems (Linux, Mac, Windows10) can be found in:

<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/availability/tutorials>

Release notes for every BioBB library release (one every quarter) can be found in the *Release Notes* section of the website (Fig. 3c):

<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/availability/release-notes>

a) Table showing BioBB packages and their associated tools and documentation links.

Package	Description	Python	ReadTheDocs	Conda	Docker	Version
biobb_amber	biobb_amber is a BioBB category for AMBER MD package, allowing setup and simulation of atomistic MD simulations using AMBER MD package and its associated AMBER tools					0.21

Building block

Building block	Wrapped tool	Description
CpptrajRandomizeIons	cpptraj	Swap specified ions with randomly selected solvent molecules using cpptraj tool from the AmberTools MD package
AmberToPDB	ambpdb	Generates a PDB structure from AMBER topology (parmtop) and coordinates (crd) files, using the ambpdb tool from the AmberTools MD package
LeapAddIons	tLeap	Adds counterions to a system box for an AMBER MD system using tLeap tool from the AmberTools MD package

b) Screenshot of the PROTEIN MD SETUP section, showing a tutorial for setting up a simulation system containing a protein, step by step, using the BioExcel Building Blocks library (biobb). The particular example used is the Lysozyme protein (PDB code 1AK).

c) Screenshot of the Release Notes section, showing the 2022.1 (17/03/2022) and 2021.4 (24/12/2021) releases.

2022.1 (17/03/2022)

- Extended information in **Python Docstrings** improving **workflow language interoperability**
- New **biobb_haddock**, a module collection to compute information-driven flexible protein-protein docking
- Released new **BioBB Workflows website**

2021.4 (24/12/2021)

- Major fixes in **biobb_common**
- Released new **BioBB REST API**

d) Screenshot of the Build Your Own Building Block (BYOBB) section, showing an interactive process flow diagram.

- Do you want to wrap up your tool with BioBB's?
- First off, please read the official documentation available at Read the Docs.
- Once you are ready, download from GitHub our biobb template.
- Use the biobb template to develop your own BioBB.
- Once you've finished and run the tests, make a pull request to our GitHub.
- Our team will check your code and, if necessary, make the appropriate arrangements.
- Once the request has been accepted, your BioBB is ready for launching.
- Congratulations! Your tool is now part of BioExcel Building Blocks!

Fig. 3. - Screenshots of the BioBB landing website. **a)** Source and Docs table, with information about all the available BioBB modules and building blocks, including links to the source code, Conda package, Docker container and Readthedocs documentation; **b)** Demonstration Workflows section, with links to all the workflow flavours in WorkflowHub (e.g. Jupyter Notebook, CWL, Python, Galaxy), source code and documentation; **c)** Release Notes section, with information on the new features added for every release; and **d)** Build Your Own Building Block (BYOBB) section, with an interactive process flow diagram.

Extended documentation on the library can be found in the *Documentation* section, including a collection of presentations from training events, a Build Your Own Building Block (BYOBB) tutorial (Fig. 3d), and a Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ):

<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/documentation/online-info>

<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/documentation/build>

<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/documentation/faqs>

A special BioBB category in the [ask.bioexcel.eu forum](https://ask.bioexcel.eu) collects questions and suggestions from our users, with direct interactions between them. The section is included in the main [BioExcel forum](https://ask.bioexcel.eu), together with the core applications and training events interaction and support.

Finally, a *Contact* specific section organizes the types of issues according to where they belong: BioBB modules, workflows, REST-API, BioBB-Wfs or generic. In all cases, the website redirects to the specific GitHub issue site.

<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/contact>

3 Demonstration Workflows

The BioBB library presented in the previous section has been specifically designed to facilitate the generation and sharing of computational biomolecular workflows, increasing the tool's interoperability and workflow reproducibility, one of the main objectives of the project. Thus, to demonstrate this for users, the library development has always been carried out concurrently with the development of demonstration workflows using them, tackling common computational biomolecular tasks and illustrating the power of the library.

The collection of demonstration workflows has considerably grown in the last period of BioExcel-2, covering now useful transversal tasks including MD setup, ligand parameterization, protein-ligand docking, free energy calculations, and DNA-specific analysis. Workflows were primarily developed using Jupyter Notebooks, and most of them have recently been converted to Galaxy, CWL and pure Python workflows.

3.1 Jupyter Notebook tutorials

Jupyter Notebooks, extensively described in previous deliverables ([D2.1](#), [D2.2](#), and [D2.3](#)) are now routinely used for documentation purposes in code development processes [21]. In BioExcel in particular, Jupyter Notebooks have proven to be a fantastic tool for on-line training events, with the possibility to use them as tutorials made of interactive programming code accompanied by text information and/or documentation, versatile graphical charts and data visualization. Besides, the combination of Jupyter Notebooks with the easy installation of the workflow dependencies using the BioBB packaging systems (Conda environment) makes our workflows highly shareable and reproducible.

BioExcel-2 deliverable 2.3 presented the first release of demonstration workflows, which included 4 Jupyter Notebooks, here expanded with implementations in other workflow systems:

- **[Protein MD Setup](#)**: Step-by-step tutorial illustrating the process of setting up a simulation system containing a protein using the GROMACS MD package.
[\[GitHub\]](#) [\[Read the Docs\]](#)
WorkflowHub flavours:
 - **Jupyter Notebook**: <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.120.2>
 - **CWL**: <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.279.1>
 - **Python**: <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.276.1>
 - **Galaxy**: <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/277?version=1>
 - **PyCOMPSs**: <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.200.1>
 - **KNIME**: <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.201.1>
- **[Automatic Ligand Parameterization](#)**: Step-by-step tutorial illustrating the process of ligand parameterization for a small molecule, using OpenBabel[11] and ACPype[12].
[\[GitHub\]](#) [\[Read the Docs\]](#)
WorkflowHub flavours:
 - **Jupyter Notebook**: <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.54.2>

- **CWL:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.255.1>
- **Python:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.280.2>
- **Galaxy:** <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/294?version=1>

- **[Protein-complex MD Setup](#):** Step-by-step tutorial illustrating the process of setting up a simulation system containing a protein in complex with a ligand, using the GROMACS MD package.

[\[GitHub\]](#) [\[Read the Docs\]](#)

WorkflowHub flavours:

- **Jupyter Notebook:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.56.3>
- **CWL:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.258.1>
- **Python:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.281.1>
- **Galaxy:** <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/295?version=1>

- **[Mutation Free Energy Calculations](#):** Step-by-step tutorial illustrating how to compute a fast-growth thermodynamic integration free energy calculation for protein mutations, using GROMACS MD package and pmx.

[\[GitHub\]](#) [\[Read the Docs\]](#)

WorkflowHub flavours:

- **Jupyter Notebook:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.55.3>
- **Python:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.328.1>

Since then, 8 new demonstration workflows have been implemented and made available through the [Workflows section](#) of the BioBB website, briefly described in the following sections. Several of these workflows have also been implemented in CWL, Python and Galaxy, as indicated below.

- **[Protein Ligand Docking \(Cluster90\)](#):** Step-by-step tutorial illustrating a protein + ligand docking process using Autodock Vina tool. Binding site automatically identified from known binding sites in similar proteins (PDB Cluster90).

[\[GitHub\]](#) [\[Read the Docs\]](#)

WorkflowHub flavours:

- **Jupyter Notebook:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.127.2>

- **[Protein Ligand Docking \(PDBe REST-API\)](#):** Step-by-step tutorial illustrating a protein + ligand docking process using Autodock Vina tool. Binding site automatically identified from information collected in the PDB Europe database (PDBe REST-API).

[\[GitHub\]](#) [\[Read the Docs\]](#)

WorkflowHub flavours:

- **Jupyter Notebook:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.128.1>

- **[Protein Ligand Docking \(FPocket\)](#):** Step-by-step tutorial illustrating a protein + ligand docking process using Autodock Vina tool. Binding site automatically identified from ligand pockets extracted using the well-known FPocket tool (FPocket).

[\[GitHub\]](#) [\[Read the Docs\]](#)

WorkflowHub flavours:

- **Jupyter Notebook:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.129.1>
- **CWL:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.259.1>

- **Python:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.282.1>
- **Galaxy:** <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/296?version=1>
- **[Amber Protein MD Setup](#):** Step-by-step tutorial illustrating the process of setting up a simulation system containing a protein using the AMBER MD package.
[\[GitHub\]](#) [\[Read the Docs\]](#)
WorkflowHub flavours:
 - **Jupyter Notebook:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.130.1>
 - **CWL:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.260.1>
 - **Python:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.283.1>
 - **Galaxy:** <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/297?version=1>
- **[Amber Protein-Ligand Complex MD Setup](#):** Step-by-step tutorial illustrating the process of setting up a simulation system containing a protein and a small molecule (protein-ligand complex) using the AMBER MD package.
[\[GitHub\]](#) [\[Read the Docs\]](#)
WorkflowHub flavours:
 - **Jupyter Notebook:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.131.1>
 - **CWL:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.261.1>
 - **Python:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.284.1>
 - **Galaxy:** <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/298?version=1>
- **[Amber Constant pH MD Setup](#):** Step-by-step tutorial illustrating the process of setting up a simulation system to run constant pH Molecular Dynamics simulations using the AMBER MD package.
[\[GitHub\]](#) [\[Read the Docs\]](#)
WorkflowHub flavours:
 - **Jupyter Notebook:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.132.1>
- **[ABC MD Setup](#):** Step-by-step tutorial illustrating the process of setting up a simulation system containing a DNA structure using the AMBER MD package, following the Ascona B-DNA Consortium (ABC) reproducible pipeline for structure preparation.
[\[GitHub\]](#) [\[Read the Docs\]](#)
WorkflowHub flavours:
 - **Jupyter Notebook:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.196.1>
 - **CWL:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.262.1>
 - **Python:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.285.1>
 - **Galaxy:** <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/299?version=1>
- **[Structural DNA Helical Parameters](#):** Step-by-step tutorial illustrating the process of setting up a simulation system containing a DNA structure using the AMBER MD package, following the Ascona B-DNA Consortium (ABC) reproducible pipeline for structure preparation.
[\[GitHub\]](#) [\[Read the Docs\]](#)
WorkflowHub flavours:
 - **Jupyter Notebook:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.195.1>
 - **Python:** <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.286.1>

The complete collection of available BioBB demonstration workflows, with links to the source code (GitHub), documentation (Readthedocs) and WorkflowHub entries, can be found in Table 2 below. A special GitHub repository is also available, gathering together the whole collection of BioBB demonstration workflows in all the different flavours:

https://github.com/bioexcel/biobb_workflows

The set of demonstration workflows will continue to be expanded with new workflows illustrating the use of new BioBB modules with every new release.

Workflow	Brief Description	GitHub	ReadThe Docs	BioBB Web	Pure Python	Jupyter Notebook	CWL	Galaxy
Protein MD Setup	Protein MD system preparation with GROMACS							
Automatic Ligand parameterization	Ligand Parameterization with ACPype							
Protein-Complex MD Setup	Protein-ligand complex MD system preparation with GROMACS							
Mutation Free Energy Calculations	Fast-growth mutation free energy calculation with GROMACS and pmx		-	-				
Protein-ligand Docking (Cluster90)	Protein-ligand docking with AutoDock Vina. Binding site identification with PDB Cluster90		-	-				
Protein-ligand Docking (PDB REST-API)	Protein-ligand docking with AutoDock Vina. Binding site identification with PDB REST-API		-	-				
Protein-ligand Docking (FPocket)	Protein-ligand docking with AutoDock Vina. Binding site identification with FPocket							
AMBER Protein MD Setup	Protein MD system preparation with AMBER							
AMBER Protein-ligand complex MD Setup	Protein-ligand Complex MD system preparation with AMBER							
AMBER Constant pH MD setup	Protein Constant pH MD system preparation with AMBER		-	-				
ABC MD setup	DNA-specific MD system preparation with AMBER							
Structural DNA helical parameters	DNA-specific MD analysis with Curves+		-	-				

Table 2.- List of currently available BioBB demonstration workflows (Release 2022.1).
<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/workflows>

3.2 Library Versatility

The collection of demonstration workflows presented in the previous section was used to validate the workflow manager-agnostic design of the BioBB library. For that, the BioBB adapters (section 2.3) were used to port the Jupyter Notebook workflows to CWL and Galaxy workflows, taking advantage of the automatically generated CWL specifications and GALAXY nodes.

In addition, pure Python workflows were also generated from the Jupyter Notebooks, using the two-files approach presented in D2.3 (Python script, YAML configuration). Finally, the demonstration workflows were also integrated in the BioBB Workflows website (section 5.2), making them available as pre-configured workflows from an easy to use integrated web-based GUI.

The different workflow implementations (which we refer to as workflow flavours) are collected in the https://github.com/bioexcel/biobb_workflows GitHub repository, and are uploaded as independent workflows in the WorkflowHub repository, providing them a unique DOI to use as a reference. As an example, the protein-Ligand docking tutorial in Jupyter Notebook can be found in the following WorkflowHub entry:

<https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/129?version=1>

and referenced with the following DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.129.1>

WorkflowHub entries for the different flavours are directly accessible from the workflows section of the BioBB website (Fig. 4). When possible, links to on-line executions are also offered (Jupyter Notebooks, GALAXY, pre-configured workflows in the BioBB-Wfs website).

PROTEIN MD SETUP 2021.2

This tutorial aims to illustrate the process of setting up a simulation system containing a protein, step by step, using the BioExcel Building Blocks library (biobb). The particular example used is the Lysozyme protein (PDB code 1AKI).

WorkflowHub Jupyter Notebook CWL Python Galaxy

Launch Jupyter Notebook * Galaxy BioBB Workflows

View tutorial Open Github repository Open documentation

gmx md protein

(*) Binder for biobb is a small installation and to promote fair use of our resources, one user is allowed to run only one notebook server at a time. Launching a new notebook server should stop the previous one. Users cannot see the notebooks run by other users, but please avoid entering secret data to the notebooks.

Fig. 4 . - Screenshot of the BioBB website Workflows section for the Protein MD Setup workflow example. From top to bottom: 1) Links to WorkflowHub entries; 2) Links to launch the workflow in live environments such as BioExcel myBinder, Galaxy or BioBB-Wfs website; and 3) links to the workflow tutorial in HTML, source code in GitHub, and documentation in Readthedocs.

This collection of demonstration workflows in different flavours exemplifies the versatility of the BioBB library, increasing the availability and reusability. Future plans include increasing the number of available demonstration workflows including new transversal examples, and also extending the number of flavours, thus supporting new popular tools in the field such as Google Colabs or Nextflow workflow manager.

4 HPC Workflows

BioExcel demonstration workflows were designed to introduce the BioBB library to the scientific community and to generate a collection of transversal workflows that could be used in combination to tackle real scientific problems. Working from these workflows, a set of more complex and powerful pipelines, focused on HTC and HPC executions, were developed in the context of the use cases (WP3, D3.3). The combination of BioBB workflows and the PyCOMPSs workflow manager enabled the generation and launching of pre-exascale workflows in HPC supercomputers, the results of which are now being considered for different scientific publications.

The initial stages of the pre-exascale workflows were presented in D2.3, whereas the final results compiled in a series of scientific paper drafts were presented in D3.6. The following sections of this deliverable present the technical information for the final versions of the workflows that have been used in these use-case studies.

4.1 Pre-exascale workflows (HPC)

The pre-exascale workflows developed during the first period of the BioExcel-2 project and presented in D2.3 were extended and improved during the last period. To briefly summarize, the most important workflows, controlled by PyCOMPSs and used in different success stories (see next section), are:

- **Molecular dynamics simulations of mutated proteins (GROMACS):** automatic modelling of protein residue mutations, MD setup preparation steps and MD production run (Fig. 5, left). Compatible with GPU-based MD simulations as well as with CPU-based MPI MD simulations.
Representative example: simulation of an Alanine scanning of a 20-residue peptide, with 20 mutations to perform, and each of the MD simulations running in 2 BSC Marenostrum nodes (2 x 48 cores), using a total of 1,920 cores in one single job.
- **Non-equilibrium alchemical free energy calculations workflow (GROMACS, pmx):** taking as an input a couple of equilibrium MD simulations (WT and mutant, previous workflow), extract an ensemble of snapshots and run fast (typically 10 to 200ps) transitions (thermodynamic integration simulations, TIs) driving the system in the forward (WT to mutant) and reverse (mutant to WT) directions. The final work values required to perform all these transitions are collected and used to calculate the free energy difference between the two states (Fig. 5, center).
Representative example: calculating a free energy difference in the folded state of a protein upon residue mutation, taking the WT and the mutated MD simulations as input, extracting an ensemble of 500 snapshots from each one, running the 1,000 TIs (500 forward + 500 reverse) and collecting the final results, distributing all the work (completely

independent short simulations) in 32 BSC Marenostrum nodes (32 x 48 cores), using a total of 1,536 cores in one single job.

- Relative ligand binding free energies upon mutations:** an extension of the previous workflow, where the whole thermodynamic cycle is computed. First, four input equilibrium trajectories should be computed for the WT and the mutated structure of both APO and HOLO systems. After that, two alchemical free energy calculation workflows are run, one for each system, to obtain the two ΔG s. The final $\Delta\Delta G$ ($\Delta G_4 - \Delta G_1$) can be then finally calculated (Fig. 5, right).

Representative example: study the effect of a human polymorphism in a protein-ligand or protein-protein binding processes, taking the WT and the mutated MD simulations (APO + HOLO) as input and running the previous workflow as a sub-workflow twice, using 64 BSC Marenostrum nodes (64 x 48 cores), using a total of 3,072 cores in one single job.

Fig. 5 - BioExcel-2 pre-exascale workflows examples. Molecular dynamics simulations of mutated proteins [Left]. Non-equilibrium alchemical free energy calculations workflow [Top Right]. Relative ligand binding free energies upon mutations [Bottom Right].

- Relative ligand binding free energies upon ligand modifications:** a revision of the previous workflows, here analysing how slight modifications on a small molecule affect the binding free energy. The main difference from the previous pipelines is a new block to analyse small molecule similarities and compute the shortest paths in a library of compounds, generating pairs of molecules with enough similarity to be able to calculate the free energy. The result of this block is a graph with nodes being the small molecules and edges being the possible transitions.

The workflow, designed by the pmx team, is particularly interesting for the pharmaceutical field, and is currently being used in a collaboration with Iktos drug discovery company (see D5.7).

Representative example: study of the binding energies for a library of compounds in a protein-ligand drug discovery process, taking the small molecules from the library, pairing them by similarity, and analysing the binding free energy as presented in the previous examples.

In all the presented cases, the execution of the workflows with the PyCOMPSs workflow manager enables the easy and flexible distribution of the work across available HPC resources.

An iterative development process allowed us to identify missing functionalities and desired features that were implemented and tested, after modifications of the BioBB library, the workflows, and also of the PyCOMPSs workflow manager. It is in the latter where the most important features were added: (a) failure tolerance, allowing the skipping of a workflow branch when problems occur, very useful for ensemble simulations where the important outcome is the number of accumulated results (e.g. histogram population), and where failures in a few cases can be neglected; (b) checkpointing, allowing the restart of the workflow after a first execution, very important for long runs, especially with HPC supercomputers having short wall-clock times; and finally (c) a new installation possibility, significantly easing the task and increasing portability across HPC centers.

All these new functionalities were tested in different supercomputers and a report is in preparation. Remarkably, one of the tests run was a scalability study (weak + strong) with up to 65,536 cores, a massive execution planned at the beginning of the project (section 7, roadmap), that demonstrates the power of the generated workflows and its importance for the executions in the new exascale machines.

The scalability study was run using the alchemical free energy calculations workflow using GROMACS and pmx, extensively described in D2.3, with polymorphisms on the human Angiotensin Converting Enzyme 2 (hACE2), the protein used by the SARS-CoV-2 virus to start the infection. Results demonstrate that BioExcel workflows are able to considerably reduce the time to results, decreasing the time needed from 65 hours in one single node (128 cores) to just 12 minutes in 512 nodes (65,536 cores) (Fig. 6). The speed-up was remarkably good up to 128 nodes (16,384 cores), decreasing slightly in the 256 and 512 nodes execution; something expected as this is completely dependent on the size of the calculated ensemble, a variable input parameter that can be tuned (fixed in this case in 1,024 simulations). The scalability study was run in the Bulgarian EuroHPC Discoverer supercomputer.

The set of BioExcel pre-exascale workflows used for the study of dynamic, scalable, reliable and portable computational biology workflows are gathered together in a BioExcel GitHub repository, with instructions on how to use them in different HPC centres (section 5.3):

https://github.com/bioexcel/biobb_hpc_workflows/tree/condapack

The last period of BioExcel-2 was dedicated to compiling and analysing all the generated data and wrapping up the use case-related projects in the form of scientific drafts. The next section presents the technical achievements of these success stories.

Fig. 6.- Scalability study using the GROMACS + pmx BioBB workflow (fast-growth free energy calculations upon protein residue mutations) controlled by PyCOMPSs. Top: Time to result from 1 to 512 nodes executions. Down: Speed-up plot. Executions done in the Discoverer supercomputer (Bulgaria), with up to 65,536 cores (128 cores x 512 nodes).

4.2 Success Stories

As presented in the D2.3 (doi:[10.5281/zenodo.4540432](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4540432)), the use cases proposed for the BioExcel-2 period, and in particular, the use case 3 (Rational Drug Design), were used to test the possibilities of the pre-exascale workflows. For the sake of avoiding repetition, please refer to D3.6 (doi:[10.5281/zenodo.6451261](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6451261)) for a brief description of the final results, and to the <https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/bioexcel-docs/docs/uc3> website for the pre-prints of the scientific works with comprehensive information. This document section is focused on the technical achievements, highlighting the pre-exascale executions.

4.2.1 Drug Sensitivity For Clinically Relevant EGFR Mutations

The first study run with the BioExcel pre-exascale workflows wanted to classify Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR) mutations by their impact on binding FDA-approved drugs, potentially predicting drug sensitivity/resistance patterns for clinically relevant EGFR mutations (Fig. 7). EGFR protein is a widely studied protein for its important role in controlling normal cell growth, apoptosis and differentiation, and mutations of EGFR can lead to abnormal activation and signal transduction causing unregulated cell division and ultimately driving some types of cancers. The pipeline could have a clear impact in personalized medicine against oncogenic mutations in EGFR, and could be possibly applicable also in other targets where resistance is an issue.

The project started with the generation of a collection of MD simulations, 10 replicas of 100ns for each APO and HOLO variant, with a final set of 310 simulations and an accumulated time of 31 μ s. From this non-negligible amount of data, 5 replicas for each system were manually selected after visual inspection, checking important binding site features, drug binding contacts, and position of important domains (P-loop, C-helix).

Finally, using these 5 replicas per system, a matrix of $\Delta\Delta G$ calculations was generated (Fig. 8), with a total of 625 free energy values to be computed for each of the variants and associated drug. Considering a typical BSC Marenostrum execution, lasting 2h with 16 nodes (768 cores), and the total number of systems in the dataset (58), a final monitored time of 2,227,200 core/h was used for the project.

Fig. 7. - Prediction of the impact of genetic variability on drug sensitivity for clinically relevant EGFR mutations schema. From the EGFR Tyrosine Kinase domain, a set of annotated drug-affecting mutations were explored by means of HPC calculations, with the aim of predicting drug sensitivity/resistance patterns that could be used in personalized treatments.

1 MUT + 1 LIG (e.g. G719S_IRE)		Mut Apo 1			Mut Apo 2			...	Mut Apo 5		
		WT Apo 1	...	WT Apo 5	WT Apo 1	...	WT Apo 5		WT Apo 1	...	WT Apo 5
Mut Hole 1	WT Hole 1	$\Delta\Delta G_1$									
	⋮										
	WT Hole 5										
Mut Hole 2	WT Hole 1										
	⋮										
	WT Hole 5										
⋮											
Mut Hole 5	WT Hole 1										
	⋮										
	WT Hole 5										$\Delta\Delta G_{625}$

Fig. 8.- Matrix of possible $\Delta\Delta G$ calculations for the EGFR project, using 5 replicas x each system (WT + variant, HOLO + APO), with a total of 625 jobs to be run.

The study was designed in the early days of BioExcel-2 as an ambitious test, requiring a large amount of disk space and calculations, with the final aim to demonstrate the power of our workflows when combined with pre-exascale resources. Results showed that the predictive power of the method was astonishingly good (Fig.9): it managed to correctly identify resistance/sensitivity patterns for all the studied variants and drug molecules, clearly beating other methods based on less sophisticated techniques such as sequence conservation or metropolis monte carlo docking approaches. Mutations were classified as resistant or sensitive according to the final $\Delta\Delta G$: a positive $\Delta\Delta G$ implied resistance, whereas a negative $\Delta\Delta G$ implied sensitivity. Those variants generating resistance were generally giving a strong sign (>5 KJ/mol), whereas those generating sensitivity were not as clear, with some uncertainties when looking at the standard errors (e.g. T790M-Osimertinib, -0.5 (+/-2.1) KJ/mol).

The final results, with information and predictive power of all tested methods can be found in the submitted article [18].

Fig. 9.- Classification of drug sensitivity for clinically relevant EGFR mutations. Mutations were classified as resistant or sensitive according to the final $\Delta\Delta G$: a positive $\Delta\Delta G$ implied resistance, whereas a negative $\Delta\Delta G$ implied sensitivity.

4.2.2 Evolutionary Path and Host-selection Mechanism of SARS-CoV-2

The second example, using the same workflow, but with an even more ambitious goal, was focused on the study of zoonotic transmission of the COVID-19 disease (see [D2.3](#)). Here the exascale project aimed to compute all the combinations between the different known viruses (RaTG13, SARS-CoV-2, SARS-CoV-1, SARS-CoV-2-US-variant) against all the different known affected species (human, bat, zibeline, pangolin, etc.). The combinatorial explosion of the calculations clearly required a massive HPC-focused project to solve.

The study started with the selection of one single pair, RaTG13 (rhinolophus affinis –horseshoe bat- virus) and SARS-CoV-2 (human virus). In a very similar way to the studies done for the previous project, calculations were run for the isolated (APO) protein (SARS-CoV-2/RaTG13 RBD and human/bat ACE2) and for the different complexes (HOLO) (SARS-CoV-2 RBD with human ACE2, SARS-CoV-2 RBD with bat ACE2, RaTG13 RBD with human ACE2 and RaTG13 RBD with bat ACE2). The spike proteins of the bat (RaTG13) and the human SARS-CoV-2 (viruses) are globally similar, but a large difference is found at the RBD domain (20 positions, 89.2% identity). These mutations constitute the main difference with the previous project, as in this case the final objective is the study of the importance and effects of these mutations making the bat and the human viruses different from each other, and by which degree they are affecting the binding with the ACE2 protein.

The pipeline consists of a set of equilibrium MD simulations with accumulated mutations, going from the bat to the human virus (and vice versa). For each of the mutations, the non-equilibrium alchemical free energy workflow is run, extracting the contribution of the particular mutation in the binding free energy. The sum of all contributions should then explain the difference in binding between the two viruses (assuming no cooperativity between the mutations) (Fig.10).

Accumulated results should be carefully interpreted, as they are also accumulating all the methodological errors for each mutation free energy calculation. For some of the cases, where unreliable numbers were found, a more refined and computationally expensive equilibrium free energy calculation was run, or the equilibrium simulation was extended/replicated (Fig. 10). These corrections and the robustness and predictive power shown by the non-equilibrium method in the previous project, together with good correlations with single variants experimental values, strengthened the reliability of the final values.

All in all, results from these massive calculations support the hypothesis of a unique evolutionary process in which SARS-CoV-2 gained the ability to directly infect humans after having developed an unusually high RBD affinity for R. affinis ACE2, its natural host receptor.

Results from this project, with extended information and methods, were included as a sub-section of the draft: *Evolutionary Path and Host-selection Mechanism of SARS-CoV-2*, (submitted), that can be found here:

https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/bioexcel-docs/data/BioExcel2_UC3_WF2/pdf

A specific PRACE COVID-19 Fast Track Proposal (*Exploring COVID-19 Infectious Mechanisms and Host Selection Process*), awarded with 6 million core-hours on Joliot-Curie supercomputer (CEA/GENCI, France) and a Spanish *Red Española de Supercomputación* (RES) proposal (*Exploring Covid19 Infectious Mechanisms and Host Selection Process*), awarded with 15 million core-hours (divided in two terms) were used for the calculations.

In summary, BioExcel pre-exascale workflows, and in particular, the non-equilibrium alchemical free energy workflow, with PyCOMPSs managing the distribution of the work along the available resources, have proved to be of utmost importance for ambitious projects requiring supercomputer power like the ones presented in these success stories.

Fig. 10 .- RaTG13 bat virus to SARS-CoV-2 human virus (and vice versa) mutation pathway. Contributions on the binding free energy per each mutation was computed and accumulated using the non-equilibrium alchemical free energy workflow. When unreliable numbers were found with this method, a refined equilibrium free energy calculation was run to correct the wrongly computed contributions (e.g. all $\Delta\Delta G$ values > 15 KJ/mol or < -15 KJ/mol after extending/replicating the equilibrium simulations were automatically classified as unreliable).

The flexibility of the workflows turned out to be crucial for the compilation of the final values in reasonable time scales. Its usage in a semi-automatic, high-throughput regime was confirmed to be effective, and opens the possibility to

explore its usage for researchers with moderate experience in molecular simulations, taking advantage of the software development best practices, including ease of use, portability, and reproducibility.

The COVID-19 study presented in this section, and the pre-exascale workflows used were included in the BioExcel review: *Pre-Exascale HPC- approaches for Molecular Dynamics simulations. Covid-19 research: a use case*, published in WIREs Computational Molecular Science. The pre-print can be found here:

https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/bioexcel-docs/data/BioExcel2_CV19_Review/pdf

The projects described were also briefly presented in the BioExcel Webinar [*BioExcel HPC Workflows: predictive power and its applications in pharmacology*](#), run in April 2022.

Workflows used in the presented projects are small variations of the ones available from the BioBB HPC Workflows GitHub repository:

https://github.com/bioexcel/biobb_hpc_workflows/tree/condapack

5 Workflows Availability

The software best practices followed in the development of the BioBB library ensure high availability and reproducibility thanks to the packaging systems, either based on Conda or Containers (Docker, Singularity). The first period of BioExcel-2 was focused on designing a protocol for our demonstration workflows, including the source code in GitHub, the documentation in Readthedocs, and an easy installation and deployment with Conda environments and our BioExcel Binder (D2.3). The second period has concentrated more on the HPC side, with the building of a PyCOMPSs Conda package and a special BioBB + PyCOMPSs Conda pack, portable across different HPC centers.

Furthermore, the availability of our BioBB workflows has been also increased thanks to a new dedicated web server (BioBB-Wfs), a programmatic interface (BioBB-API), and the BioBB Galaxy instance (<https://biobb.usegalaxy.es/>). Finally, all workflows developed in the project have been uploaded to the WorkflowHub workflows repository, receiving a unique DOI identifier, with which they can be properly shared and cited. The next sections summarise the current available ways for our users to access and test our workflows.

5.1 Local installation (Conda)

The Jupyter Notebook demonstration workflows presented in section 2 are all accompanied with a special Conda environment file, containing all the workflow dependencies, included in the GitHub repository. These dependencies are installed with one single command line command, provided that the user already has the Conda packaging system tool installed in the system (the only requirement to install and run BioBB workflows). It is the recommended option for local deployment, and has been successfully tested and used in different training events.

In general, this approach works well, although installations of the Conda environment take a while for workflows with many dependencies, a minor issue considering that the process is run just once. As with all technologies, though, it is not a universal solution. We have found some incompatibilities when working with old machines or Operating Systems (e.g. glibc old versions). Additionally, most of the Conda packages are still not compatible with architectures such as the IBM Power9. In these cases, the local installation of the software tools must be used, with the special “*binary_path*” BioBB property, present in all the building blocks.

5.2 HPC installation (HPC modules, Conda Pack)

During the first period of BioExcel-2, the BioBB library was installed as a new module in the BSC supercomputers. This way, with a simple “*module load biobb*” command line, the whole collection of BioBB building blocks were available. This solution, however convenient from a user point of view, turned out not to be feasible for all the HPC centers and supercomputers, as the creation of new modules usually needs to follow a very restrictive protocol. Trying to

solve this issue, a new method was tested: Conda packs. A Conda pack is an archive of a particular Conda environment that can be installed on other systems and locations, even in systems without Conda packaging software installed. A Conda pack is basically a special tgz-formatted file containing a whole Conda environment, portable across different computers with the same architecture. To test the performance and reliability of the method, a Conda pack with the whole BioBB v3.6 library and the PyCOMPSs v2.9 workflow manager was generated in the BSC Marenostrum supercomputer and then moved to different machines (Cirrus, Juwels, Jusuf, Starlife, Lusitania, Discoverer). The use of this Conda pack extraordinarily eased the installation process: just copying the tgz file, decompressing it and running a conda-unpack command line process installs the whole library, generating a new Conda environment in the machine. This extremely easy three-step process was included in the instructions of the BioBB HPC workflows GitHub repository (in a new [condapack](#) branch).

Once the Conda environment with the BioBB library and PyCOMPSs workflow manager is installed, the BioBB HPC workflows repository can be cloned and tested, with just one last process to be manually modified: the [supercomputer configuration file](#), which presents to PyCOMPSs the supercomputer (e.g. CPU/GPU, cores x node, memory, scratch folder) and associated queue manager (e.g. partitions, MPI environment, projects) configuration parameters. Examples for the previously mentioned Cirrus, Juwels, Jusuf, Starlife, Lusitania and Discoverer supercomputers are already available in the [GitHub configuration file](#).

Given the good results obtained with this methodology, it will be further tested in our following HPC projects. New Conda packs will be generated with the new BioBB and/or PyCOMPSs releases, with the last one being the BioBB v3.7 + PyCOMPSs v.2.9.2, available here:

<https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb/condapacks/biobb37.tar.gz>

5.3 Web-based interfaces

Web interfaces are a must for every project nowadays. We are constantly connected to the Internet, expecting to find information for any query we might have. For IT projects in particular, having a website is always the first priority. BioExcel has worked with this important point since the first period, building not only advertising our landing websites (e.g. [BioExcel](#), [BioBB](#)), but also web-based GUIs from which our users could access and execute our demonstration workflows.

The fast evolution of the informatics technology, with current network bandwidths allowing streaming of heavy videos at home, Central and Graphics Processing Units (CPUs, GPUs) powerful enough to work with extremely demanding tasks, even in portable and small devices, and new and powerful web development methodologies and languages, allows the building of complex, interactive and easy to use web platforms. The next sections briefly describe the

collection of web-based interfaces giving access to the BioBB demonstration workflows.

5.3.1 BioExcel Cloud Portal (myBinder)

One of the main objectives of WP2 has always been the provisioning of a workflow environment, where our users could find, access and if possible, execute our developed workflows. With this goal in mind, the [BioExcel Cloud Portal](#) was developed in the BioExcel-1 period. The web portal is directly connected to the European Bioinformatics repository ([bio.tools](#)), and presents to our users the different BioExcel tools, Virtual Machines (VMs), and workflows.

The portal was successfully used in the BioExcel-1 period in different training events, with participants deploying BioExcel VMs and connecting to them using standard ssh connections. Extended information about the BioExcel Cloud Portal was included in the BioExcel-1 D2.4 deliverable (doi:[10.5281/zenodo.3236256](#)).

The BioExcel-2 period started with an analysis of the new state of the art technologies, methods and tools applicable to the computational biomolecular field. This included an analysis of hardware and software technologies, which identified two prominent technologies: containers (Docker, Singularity) and Jupyter Notebooks. Both technologies were added in the WP2 roadmap, and have been extensively used since then.

Jupyter Notebooks have become tremendously popular among researchers and data scientists, and are particularly interesting for this section. Briefly, they are an extension of the iPython initiative, extending the console-based interactive shell with a web-based application with which programmers can develop, document, execute code, and share results. Extended information can be found in the previous D2.1 (doi:[10.5281/zenodo.4604607](#)), D2.2 (doi:[10.5281/zenodo.4605207](#)) and D2.3 (doi:[10.5281/zenodo.4540432](#)) deliverables. The possibility of combining the power of the Jupyter Notebooks with Conda environments, allowing an automatic deployment of our demonstration workflows in infrastructures such as [myBinder](#), was really useful for our workflow provisioning purpose.

Thus, during the first period of BioExcel-2, the demonstration workflows were made compatible with myBinder infrastructure, with new links being added in the [BioBB landing website](#), and the possibility for our users to directly deploy the Jupyter Notebooks and start playing with them. However, we soon realised that myBinder, being a free service, was not suitable for more complex cases such as computationally demanding pipelines (e.g. MD Setup) or training events (with many instances possibly running at the same time).

For this purpose, a local implementation of the MyBinder platform ([BinderHub](#)) was installed and configured within the BioExcel Cloud Portal infrastructure, allowing us to link our demonstration tutorials to a private, controlled infrastructure, overcoming possible overload problems of the public MyBinder

server. The new infrastructure has proved to be very useful, to the point that it has been recently extended outside of the BioBB tutorials, and is now also running the official [GROMACS tutorials](#) (developed in the BioExcel-2 period). Two different implementations of the myBinder infrastructure were deployed:

- **Open-access Binder**, accessible from the [BioBB workflows section](#) and the [GROMACS tutorials](#) websites, with a simple GitHub authentication. Statistics from 2021 captured more than 100 different users and more than 500 notebooks launched.
- **Training instance Binder**, specially designed for training events, with restricted access and shared disk to distribute documentation and files.

The Binder infrastructure under the hood leverages the potential of container and cloud technologies by being built on top of Kubernetes (k8s), the most popular container orchestration system and using container and Kubernetes-based tools and infrastructure such as DockerHub, Helm, Helmsman, Grafana and Fluentd for k8s. It is currently hosted in the EMBL-EBI private OpenStack cloud, but the use of Kubernetes and deployment automations, guarantees portability between cloud infrastructures and will enable installation of satellite deployments at other partners' sites or in the public cloud (Cloud agnostic approach). In fact, a clone of the BioExcel Binder has already started to be deployed in the BSC premises, ensuring sustainability of the portal in future BioExcel periods.

The Binder infrastructure has become one of the most popular web-based interface contributions of the BioExcel-2 period, being used in most of the BioBB training events, including the Spring and Summer schools (section 6.1), and showing interest from important communities such as the ELIXIR structural community ([3D-BioInfo](#)).

5.3.2 BioBB-Wfs

An alternative way of accessing and executing our workflows is a dedicated web-based platform, the BioBB Workflows website ([BioBB-Wfs](#)) [11]. Designed taking as a reference a popular but currently old project ([MDWeb](#)), and primarily oriented to entry-level users, BioBB-Wfs offers the collection of demonstration workflows in a web-based GUI with a high level of interactivity, integration with the NGL viewer to visualize and check 3D structures, MDsrv to visualize trajectories, and Plotly to explore 2D plots.

Interestingly, the available workflows can be launched in the platform, thanks to the underlying on-demand private cloud infrastructure (Fig. 11) or downloaded to be run in the users' own premises. In the latter case, two different BioBB workflow flavours are generated and offered to the user: CWL and Pure Python, increasing reproducibility and reusability. Finally, remote launching of long executions to user's available High-Performance computers is also possible, with just an easy configuration of the appropriate access credentials through the web portal.

Fig. 11. - BioBB Workflows web server schema, including an on-demand private cloud infrastructure to execute the pre-configured workflows, and the MDSrv server to stream the generated or uploaded MD trajectories

From a user's point of view, and in comparison to the Jupyter Notebooks executions, the BioBB-Wfs server is offering a most detailed experience with specific information for each of the pipelines. As an example, the server offers specific intermediate steps to extract required or useful information for each particular workflow: for the protein-ligand docking workflow, pockets are computed on the fly in the input structure for the user to select the most appropriate one for the final docking process; a structure-checking process allows to select the components of the structures to be included in the MD setup workflows (e.g. chains, alternative conformations), showing at the same time a comprehensive series of possible issues (e.g. wrong amide atoms assignments or VdW clashes) in the input structure that can affect MD simulation.

Another advantage of the server is the possibility to register and create a personal user's workspace, storing and organizing all the inputs, outputs and workflows launched, which can also be easily shared with other colleagues through a standard URL (Fig. 12). Moreover, launching simulations to external HPC machines is only available to registered users, as the connection details and credentials are stored in the user's profile.

More information can be found in the [BioBB-Wfs paper](#) [11].

BioBB-Wfs Website: <https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb-wfs/>

The screenshot displays the BioBB Galaxy user interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Workflows', and 'Help' on the left, and 'Contact' and 'My Projects' on the right. The 'My Projects' section is highlighted. Below the navigation bar, the page title is 'List of projects'. A progress bar at the top indicates the usage of various projects: 1AKI GROMACS Set Up (2.12%), ABC MD Setup (1.42%), 3HTB - JZ4 GROMACS Complex Set Up (2.85%), and Structural DNA helical parameters (16.37%). The main content area shows a table of projects with columns for Name, Status, Creation date, Expiration date, Size, and Actions. The table lists four projects, all with a status of 'WF FINISHED'. A search bar and a filter dropdown are located above the table. The table shows 20 records and displays 1 to 4 of 4 entries.

Name	Status	Creation date	Expiration date	Size	Actions
Structural DNA helical parameters	WF FINISHED	13/01/2022 12:37	PERSISTENT	838.28 MB	Project actions
3HTB - JZ4 GROMACS Complex Set Up	WF FINISHED	13/01/2022 12:27	PERSISTENT	145.80 MB	Project actions
ABC MD Setup	WF FINISHED	13/01/2022 12:25	PERSISTENT	72.63 MB	Project actions
1AKI GROMACS Set Up	WF FINISHED	13/01/2022 12:23	PERSISTENT	108.59 MB	Project actions

Fig. 12.- BioBB-Wfs user's workspace. (A) List of projects; (B) user profile; (C) my projects (workspace) instant access.

5.3.3 BioBB Galaxy

[Galaxy](#) is a popular web-based GUI to build and run bioinformatics workflows. With more than 15 years of activity so far, it is one of the most recognized platforms in the field, and its ecosystem is still expanding. The Galaxy ToolShed, an "appstore" for tool developers and Galaxy admins to host and share Galaxy tools (nodes, building blocks), is now including more than 5500 tools. With a main focus on accessibility, reproducibility, reusability and portability, it has become a reference tool for projects such as ELIXIR and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

The Galaxy project maintains a central interface (usegalaxy.org, supported by NIH and NSF), the Galaxy Europe (usegalaxy.eu, supported by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research) and the Galaxy Australia (usegalaxy.org.au, supported by Bioplatforms Australia and the Australian Research Data Commons). But the platform was developed with the aim of making it easy to be cloned and used for specific projects. Thus, a great number of Galaxy public servers (instances) exist, either related to different countries (usegalaxy.es, usegalaxy.fr, usegalaxy.no), or focusing on particular studies (chemoinformatics.usegalaxy.eu, ml.usegalaxy.eu).

The biobb.usegalaxy.es is a new Galaxy instance, including all the BioBB building blocks. Deployed and maintained by the BSC partner, it is powered by the Starlife private Cloud infrastructure, allowing executions of biomolecular simulation workflows. The collection of BioBB demonstration workflows were converted to Galaxy workflows and can be imported and launched after registering into the platform. New workflows can be easily built with the Galaxy drag & drop

interface, connecting building blocks and setting the proper parameters. Installation of all software dependencies is managed by the Conda packages.

The next step and final goal of this project is the upload of the BioBB building blocks into the Galaxy ToolShed, so that the library utilities can be accessed from the central Galaxy instances, opening the possibility to generate complex workflows mixing the BioBB building blocks with the large number of currently existing Galaxy nodes. The automatic generation of the BioBB Galaxy xml nodes (section 2.3) was a big step forward for this task, as it ensures a quick update of the Galaxy nodes with new BioBB releases.

5.3.4 BioBB-API

Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), tools allowing programmatic access to data and services, are being more common every day, with Representational State Transfer (REST API) as the most commonly used API architecture, mainly due to its compatibility with many data formats, including JavaScript Object Notation (JSON). APIs have been routinely integrated in life science projects where transfer of data is required. What is not so common is the use of REST API technology to offer remote execution services instead of just data (*Software as a Service* – SaaS).

Taking advantage of the automatic protocol to transform documentation into adapters (section 2.3), the collection of BioBB building blocks were converted to REST API endpoints, giving programmatic access to all the functionalities integrated in the library, and building the BioBB-API platform [12].

As with the previously presented BioBB-Wfs server, the BioBB REST API is powered by an on-demand private cloud infrastructure, deploying new Virtual Machines when needed (Fig. 13). Tools are executed in asynchronous mode, as the time to completion is usually unknown and will depend on the tool and the available resources. Thus, endpoints should be called in three steps: launch, poll, and data retrieval (Fig. 13).

Generic endpoints are available from the base BioBB REST API URL <https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb-api/rest/v1>, whereas the complete list of endpoints are available from the BioBB REST API Tools Endpoints URL <https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb-api/tools-documentation>

The BioBB-API can be then used to execute BioBB workflows without the need of installing any tool. An example of a BioBB-API workflow, reproducing the MD setup tutorial <https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb-api/tutorials/mdsetup> shows how to use the API using a graphical interface such as Jupyter Notebooks.

More information can be found in the BioExcel REST-API paper [12].

The BioBB-API Website: <https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/biobb-api/>

Fig. 13 - BioBB REST API user's interaction diagram. API endpoints executions comprise three different steps: launch, poll, and data retrieval. The launch process involves sending the input data files, with the endpoint returning a token id (asynchronous execution). The token is then used to query for the job status (Polling request). Once the execution is finished, a set of output id(s) (unique identifiers) for the generated data are sent, and can be used to retrieve the final results (Output request).

5.4 WorkflowHub

Finally, BioExcel-2 collaborated with different European projects, including ELIXIR and EOSC-Life, in the creation of a workflows repository: [WorkflowHub \[3\]](#). Unlike the European tools registry ([bio.tools](#)), this registry focuses on describing, sharing and publishing scientific computational workflows, using extensive use of open standards and tools, including Common Workflow Language (CWL) [15], RO-Crate [13], BioSchemas and GA4GH Tool Registry Service (TRS) [19], in accordance with the FAIR principles.

All the demonstration workflows presented in this document, as well as all the workflows included in the BioBB-Wfs web server have been uploaded to WorkflowHub. Thanks to this, now all of them can be properly cited or referenced using the DOI assigned by the platform. Besides, a downloadable RO-Crate [8] object is generated for each of the workflows, including the workflow source code files, metadata, and sample files, if available. Different workflow flavours can be uploaded in the repository: Jupyter Notebooks, CWL, Pure Python, Galaxy, etc. Depending on the type, the uploaded files are parsed and useful information is automatically extracted and presented in the web interface (e.g. CWL workflow diagram).

The complete collection of BioBB workflows available from WorkflowHub (48 as of May 2022) can be obtained with this link:

<https://workflowhub.eu/workflows?filter%5Bproject%5D=11>

WorkflowHub allows entries to be in different states including "In Progress"¹ before finally assigning DOIs. These BioBB entries have been deemed Stable:

¹ For instance, BioBB Galaxy Workflows currently only install on biobb.usegalaxy.es, see section 7.

- **Jupyter Notebook:** Automatic Ligand Parameterization tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.54.2>]
- **CWL:** Automatic Ligand Parameterization tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.255.1>]
- **Jupyter Notebook:** Mutation Free Energy Calculations using BioExcel Building Blocks (biobb) [a href="https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.55.2">https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.55.2]
- **Jupyter Notebook:** GROMACS Protein Ligand Complex MD Setup tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.56.2>]
- **CWL:** GROMACS Protein Ligand Complex MD Setup tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.258.1>]
- **Jupyter Notebook:** GROMACS Protein MD Setup tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.120.2>]
- **CWL:** GROMACS Protein MD Setup tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.29.3>]
- **Galaxy:** GROMACS Protein MD Setup tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.194.1>]
- **PyCOMPS:** GROMACS Protein MD Setup HPC tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.200.1>]
- **KNIME:** GROMACS Protein MD Setup tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.201.1>]
- **Jupyter Notebook:** Protein-ligand Docking tutorial (Cluster90)
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.127.2>]
- **Jupyter Notebook:** Protein-ligand Docking tutorial (PDBe REST API)
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.128.1>]
- **Jupyter Notebook:** Protein-ligand Docking tutorial (Fpocket)
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.129.1>]
- **Galaxy:** Protein-ligand Docking tutorial (Fpocket)
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.257.1>]
- **CWL:** Protein-ligand Docking tutorial (Fpocket)
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.259.1>]
- **Jupyter Notebook:** AMBER Protein MD Setup tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.130.1>]
- **CWL:** AMBER Protein MD Setup tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.260.1>]
- **Jupyter Notebook:** Amber Protein Ligand Complex MD Setup tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.131.1>]
- **CWL:** Amber Protein Ligand Complex MD Setup tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.261.1>]
- **Jupyter Notebook:** Amber Constant pH MD Setup tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.132.1>]
- **Jupyter Notebook:** Structural DNA helical parameters tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.195.1>]
- **Jupyter Notebook:** ABC MD Setup tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.196.1>]
- **CWL:** ABC MD Setup tutorial
[<https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.262.1>]

6 Workflows Visibility & uptake

BioExcel workflows, and in particular, the BioBB library, although being now a mature technology, are still young. It started as a prototype in BioExcel-1, and has evolved since then into a technology that can now be used in real scientific projects, as shown in section 4. During the last period of the BioExcel-2 project, coinciding with the completion of the use cases studies, the efforts for advertising and sharing the power of the library and its associated workflows have increased, with a number of training events run, scientific works published or in preparation, and webinars and talks given in international conferences. Although changing old habits is a difficult process, we think that the library is now ready to help our community in building FAIR workflows, and we are expecting an increase in the uptake in the coming years.

6.1 Training Events

The BioBB library has been presented in depth in three Virtual Training sessions (presented in D4.4), one per BioExcel-2 year:

- [Virtual Training #1](#)
- [Virtual Training #2](#)
- [Virtual Training #3](#)

The Virtual Trainings (VTs) allowed us to enter in detail and explain step by step how to build a workflow using the library and a Jupyter Notebook interface. Interestingly, after receiving participant's feedback in the first VT about the possibility to extend the training to explore different flavours other than Jupyter Notebook, a command line interface (Pure Python) workflow was added in the following VTs, that were also extended from two to three days.

The BioBB demonstration workflows, and in particular, the GROMACS MD setup and GROMACS protein+ligand complex MD setup, have been used in many workshops, as listed here. BioBB workflows have been officially show-cased in the key BioExcel school events, together with our key applications GROMACS, HADDOCK, pmx and CP2K, a great achievement.

- [BioExcel Summer School 2020 \(Remote\)](#)
- [BioExcel Summer School 2021 \(Remote\)](#)
- [BioExcel Summer School 2022](#)
- [BioExcel Winter School 2020 \(Remote\)](#)
- [CSC Advanced GROMACS Workshop 2021 \(Remote\)](#)
- [CSC Advanced GROMACS Workshop 2022 \(Remote\)](#)
- [Integrative Approach to the theoretical study of Chromatin 2022](#)
- [PATC: Introduction to simulation environments for Life Sciences 2020](#)
- [PATC: Introduction to simulation environments for Life Sciences 2021](#)
- [PATC: Introduction to simulation environments for Life Sciences 2022](#)

These demonstration workflows have had a good reception in the field, exemplified here by a tweet by Professor Syma Khalid from the University of Oxford, saying that “*The BioExcelCoE online tutorials are exceptional – just adapting the gromacs simulation set up one using biobb building blocks for undergrad and grad level teaching*” (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14 .- Tweet by Prof. Syma Kahlid, talking about the BioExcelCoE BioBB demonstration workflows and its possibilites in teaching purposes

Also important for our visibility, the BioBB library and its ecosystem were presented in different BioExcel meetings with pharmaceutical companies organized by the WP5, with a special virtual training organized for Astra Zeneca.

6.2 Draft papers, conferences, webinars

Visibility and recognition in our field are mainly achieved through prestigious scientific publications and conference talks. Even when talking about technology, a tool is starting to be renowned after it has been published and starts to receive citations from external works. The BioBB library was published at the beginning of the BioExcel-2 period (2019), and is starting to be [cited now](#) (24 citations as of June 2022). The collection of [BioBB Conda packages](#) have already past the 100,000 downloads (with the most requested category being the `biobb_analysis`, with 19,236 downloads), demonstrating the interest for these solutions in our field. The second period of BioExcel-2 has concentrated on wrapping-up the BioBB side-projects and the scientific studies using BioBB workflows, trying to convert them into publications. Showing the power of the BioBB’s workflows should help increase its visibility, and in turn, its uptake. The collection of drafts, some of them already published, some of them submitted, and some of them in final stages, have been gathered together in a special website: <https://mmb.irbbarcelona.org/bioexcel-docs/>. The website is divided in three groups: Use Case 3, WP2 and BioBB.

The scientific studies done in the context of the Use Case 3 and using the BioExcel pre-exascale workflows are:

- [Evolutionary Path and Host-selection Mechanism of SARS-CoV-2](#), *submitted*.
- [DNAffinity: A Machine-Learning Approach To Predict Dna Binding Affinities Of Transcription Factors](#), *in revision*.
- [Pre-Exascale HPC-approaches for Molecular Dynamics simulations. Covid-19 research: a use case](#) [20], published (DOI: [10.1002/wcms.1622](#)).
- [Enabling the execution of large-scale workflows for molecular dynamics simulations](#), *in preparation*.
- [Prediction Of The Impact Of Genetic Variability On Drug Sensitivity For Clinically Relevant EGFR Mutations](#) [18], *submitted*.

The project reports for the WP2, in form of deliverables, summarizing the work done in the context of BioExcel workflows, usability, deployment and scalability are:

- [D2.1 – State of the Art and Initial Roadmap](#)
(DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4604607](#))
- [D2.2 - First release of workflow-ready building blocks library](#)
(DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4605207](#))
- [D2.3 – First release of demonstration workflows](#)
(DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4540432](#))
- [D2.4 – Development of a framework for the combination of HPC and HPDA operations](#)
(DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4916029](#))
- [D2.5 - Provision of a Workflow Environment at BioExcel portal](#)
(DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4916060](#))
- [D2.6 – Integration of BioExcel software framework with standards and international initiatives](#)
(DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5824544](#))

And finally, the publications of the BioBB library and its side-projects, extending the BioBB ecosystem and increasing the BioBB visibility:

- [BioExcel Building Blocks, a software library for interoperable biomolecular simulation workflows](#) [1], *published*.
(DOI: [10.1038/s41597-019-0177-4](#))
- [Making Canonical Workflow Building Blocks interoperable across workflow languages](#) [14], *published*.
(DOI: [10.1162/dint a 00135](#))
- [BioExcel Building Blocks Workflows \(BioBB-Wfs\), an integrated web-based platform for biomolecular simulations](#) [11], *published*.
(DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkac380](#))
- [BioExcel Building Blocks REST API \(BioBB REST API\), programmatic access to interoperable biomolecular simulation tools](#) [12], *published*.
(DOI: [10.1093/bioinformatics/btac316](#))

The BioBB pre-exascale workflows were also presented in renowned international conferences and webinars such as the CECAM extraordinary

COVID-19 webinars “[HPC and BigData approaches in CoVid-19 research](#)”, and “[BioExcel Building Blocks and HPC. A test case in CoVID Research](#)”, both given by prof. Modesto Orozco. Finally, a summary of the predictive power of the BioExcel pre-exascale workflows was presented in the BioExcel Webinar series: “[BioExcel HPC Workflows: predictive power and its applications in pharmacology](#)”, by Adam Hospital, Milosz Wieczór and Federica Battistini.

6.3 Integration with Standards & International initiatives

Visibility and uptake is also reached through collaborations with standards and international initiatives. BioExcel has been highly active in these collaborations since its foundation, with special connections with the ELIXIR European project and most recently with the EOSC infrastructure and its Life Science part (EOSC-Life). A summary of the active engagement of BioExcel with ongoing initiatives was presented in the previous deliverable D2.6 (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5824544](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5824544)).

A particularly important connection with international initiatives is the one involving the newly constituted [Workflows Community Initiative](#) (WCI), with UNIMAN and BSC as founding partners and leading two important sections of the community: [FAIR Computational Workflows](#) (Carole Goble) and Systems and Applications Performance (Rosa M. Badia). The WCI wants to bring the workflows community together (*users, developers, researchers, and facilities*) to engage in community-wide efforts to tackle workflows grand challenges.

Another important and recent collaboration is the one started with the ELIXIR structural community ([3D-BioInfo](#)), where our reproducible workflows will be used as a reference to build and share the pipelines used for an implementation study trying to characterize the conformational landscape of native proteins from similar structures in the PDB database. The discussions started in this project allowed us to show the possibilities of the BioBB FAIR software development and convince the structural community about the importance of interoperable and reproducible software. On the bad side, it also brought to light the still existing problem of lack of standards in the field, an issue that was explored in BioExcel-1 [22] and that should be tackled in the near future.

And finally, the great collaboration with the WorkflowHub, the official workflow repository for the EOSC-Life project, has resulted in [48 BioExcel workflows](#) registered. The registration process has been a good test for the portal, gathering feedback from the uploading of different workflow flavours (Jupyter Notebook, Galaxy, CWL, Pure Python), with source code, configurations files, metadata, and sample data, and extending the RO-Crate objects with this information.

7 Final Roadmap

The first WP2 deliverable in the BioExcel-2 period (D2.1, [10.5281/zenodo.4604607](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4604607)) presented an initial roadmap for the first 18 months of the BioExcel workflows package. The roadmap contained explicit objectives and milestones that were revised in the D2.2 ([10.5281/zenodo.4605207](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4605207)) and D2.3 documents ([10.5281/zenodo.4540432](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4540432)), with new objectives and new (or updated) milestones included. In this section we present the final roadmap, with comments and conclusions on the planned milestones at the end of the BioExcel-2 period. Milestones added in the roadmap updates presented in D2.2 and D2.3 are tagged with the “[New]” prefix in the table.

As a summary, 38 out of 45 milestones from the ambitious roadmap proposed have been *completed* or *partially completed*. Milestones tagged as *partially completed* are usually milestones built up from a number of projects, some of them added in the roadmap revisions (D2.2 and D2.3). An example can be the T2.1 milestones, including the integration of a big number of tools into the BioBB library. In these cases, *partially completed* implies that not all tools could be integrated. The table expands on which ones were finally integrated and the reasons behind the ones that could not be integrated. T2.6 (retaining usability, interoperability, and reproducibility in Exascale workflows) was particularly challenging, as the tools chosen in the state of the art analysis done at the beginning of the project (D2.1) have finally proved to be not suitable for efficient HPC calculations (e.g. CWL, KNIME, Galaxy). Additionally, promising CWL features (e.g. provenance, workflow managers compatibility) are evolving at a slow pace, and were not ready to be used in the BioExcel-2 period. These milestones were tagged as partially completed, as they were investigated until missing features were found.

For the rest of the milestones, important issues were found hindering the accomplishment of the proposed studies. As an example, the milestone proposing the creation of a KNIME CWL node executing containers remotely on multiple hosts was revised and finally substituted for a different work on Galaxy GUI, after an initial investigation of the KNIME table-based data model, very inefficient for molecular dynamics data. Some of these milestones were also redefined due to the pandemic, as for example the implementation of demonstration workflows showing HPC/HPDA convergence, that was substituted by the BioExcel-CV19 HPDA project.

The roadmap has been an important part of the work package, a reference document guiding the development of the BioExcel workflows from the start.

T2.1 - Application building blocks for computational biomolecular simulations		
Objective A: Building Blocks for the main codes: HADDOCK, pmx, and CP2K		
Milestones	Status	Comment
<p><i>(A1) Implement building blocks for pmx</i></p> <p><i>(A2) Build a free-energy workflow integrating GROMACS & pmx</i></p> <p><i>(A3) Make the workflow available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p> <p><i>[New] (A4) Implement building blocks for HADDOCK; build a docking workflow; make it available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p> <p><i>[New] (A5) Implement building blocks for CP2K; build a QM workflow; make it available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p>	PARTIALLY COMPLETED	<p>Milestones A1, A2 and A3 were completed (D2.2). The creation of building blocks for pmx was a priority for the project and the non-equilibrium alchemical free energy calculations workflow combining GROMACS and pmx has been used in scientific projects needing millions of core/hours in HPC resources (section 4).</p> <p>Milestone A4 was divided in two stages. The first stage involved the generation of a docking workflow with HADDOCK v2 packaged in a singularity container and PyCOMPSs controlling it. The second stage involved the generation of the building blocks for the new HADDOCK v3. This last stage was started late in the project, and is an ongoing effort, in parallel with the development of the new modular HADDOCK v3 version.</p> <p>Milestone A5 was started, with the generation of the first CP2K building blocks. However, problems with the CP2K Conda package (missing functionalities) have hindered the development. Exploring possibilities such as generating a new Conda package or Docker container.</p>
Objective B (cont.): Building Blocks for the development of the Rational Drug Design use case		
Milestones	Status	Comment
<p><i>(B1) Implement building blocks for chemistry tools</i></p> <p><i>(B2) Build a ligand parameterization workflow using the new biobb category</i></p> <p><i>(B3) Make the workflow available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p> <p><i>[New] (B4) Update the biobb_vs module with new building blocks; build a protein-ligand docking workflow; make it available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p> <p><i>[New] (B5) Implement building</i></p>	PARTIALLY COMPLETED	<p>Milestones B1, B2 and B3 were completed (D2.2). Chemoinformatics tools such as OpenBabel and ACPype were integrated in the library and an automatic parameterization workflow was built and used as a sub-workflow for the protein-ligand MD setup demonstration workflows for GROMACS and AMBER. It is also integrated in the BioBB-Wfs web server.</p> <p>Milestone B4 was completed. The biobb_vs was updated with new building blocks wrapping the Autodock Vina docking tool and also the FPocket tool for automatic finding of pockets in the surface of the protein. Both tools were integrated in a protein-ligand demonstration workflow. Two additional workflows were also generated, with different ways of finding pockets, one through pockets in similar proteins (PDB Cluster90) and another one through information taken from the PDB REST API.</p> <p>Milestone B5 was partially completed. A new biobb_cmip module was created, wrapping different functionalities from the CMIP tool such as Molecular Interaction Potentials</p>

<p><i>blocks to compute Classical Molecular Interactions Potentials (CMIP); build a demonstration workflow; make it available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p> <p><i>[New] (B6) Update the biobb_chemistry module with new building blocks; build a demonstration workflow; make it available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p> <p><i>[New] (B7) Update the biobb_md module; build a demonstration workflow; make it available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p>		<p>and titration (positioning of water molecules and ions in the most energetically favourable spots on the surface of the protein). A demonstration workflow is in preparation, and will be made available before the end of the project.</p> <p>Milestone B6 and B7 are delayed. The integration of new tools such as RDKit and plumed are still on the plans, but it was not possible during the BioExcel-2 period. The possibility to run enhanced sampling simulations (plumed) and free energy calculations upon ligand modifications with pmx (using RDKit) are top priorities for our plans.</p>
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Objective C (cont.): Building Blocks for the development of High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA)

Milestones	Status	Comment
<p><i>(C1) Implement building blocks for HPDA tools, wrapping dislib utilities</i></p> <p><i>(C2) Build an HPDA workflow prototype using the new biobb category</i></p> <p><i>(C3) Make the workflow available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p> <p><i>[New] (C4) Implement building blocks wrapping Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) tools; build demonstration workflows; make them available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p>	<p>PARTIALLY REDEFINED, PARTIALLY COMPLETED</p>	<p>Milestones C1, C2 and C3 were partially redefined. As the Dislib library was not designed to deal with MD trajectory data, the task was redefined and the integration of Dislib in the BioBB library was put on hold. Instead, the task focused on 1) extending the Dislib library to read MD trajectories; 2) benchmark the PCA Dislib utility against popular tools in our field (MDtraj, MDAnalysis, ProDy, etc.), analysing both the differences in the resulting eigen values and eigen vectors, and the computational efficiency. The goal is to demonstrate the advantage of using a distributed calculation with Dislib in big structures and/or long trajectories.</p> <p>Milestone C4 was completed (D2.4). A new biobb_ml module was created and used in a scientific project defined in the use case 3 (DNAffinity, section 6.2). Milestone C5 is ongoing, with the conversion of the workflows run in the project into demonstration workflows, adding documentation and making them more didactic. Expected to be made available by the end of the project.</p>

Objective D: Maintain, update and extend biobb modules

Milestones	Status	Comment
<p><i>(D1) Update the biobb_analysis module with new building blocks; build demonstration workflows; make them</i></p>	<p>PARTIALLY COMPLETED</p>	<p>Milestone D1, D2 and D3 were partially completed.</p> <p>The biobb_analysis module was not extended, but a new module, collecting DNA-specific analysis, was created:</p>

<p><i>available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p> <p><i>(D2) Update the biobb_io module with new building blocks; build demonstration workflows; make them available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p> <p><i>(D3) Update the biobb_pmx module adding new building blocks to support nucleic acids and ligand modifications; build demonstration workflows; make them available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p>		<p>biobb_dna. This new module contains 17 different building blocks, that were used to generate a new demonstration workflow: the Structural DNA helical parameters.</p> <p>Several new building blocks were added to the biobb_io module, such as queries to the PDBe REST API, MemProtMD database, and the RCSB PDB REST API. The new building blocks are used in different demonstration workflows such as the protein-ligand docking ones.</p> <p>The biobb_pmx module was slightly modified to make it compatible with nucleic acids modifications. However, ligand modifications are still not available. Its implementation is a priority for our plans.</p>
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T2.2 Definition, development and specification of workflow prototypes

Objective A: Workflow prototype: Structural conformations from a small molecule

Objective B: Workflow prototype: Virtual screening with binding free energies

Objective C: Workflow prototype: HPDA methods combined with HPC calculations

Milestones	Status	Comment
<p><i>A1, B1, C1. Implement demonstration workflow as a Jupyter Notebook</i></p> <p><i>A2, B2, C2. Prepare the workflow to be used with PyCOMPSs and CWL</i></p> <p><i>A3, B3, C3. Make the workflow available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p>	PARTIALLY COMPLETED, REDEFINED	<p>The objectives proposed for this task were substantially reformulated during the first half of the project after revising the work planned for the first period of BioExcel-2 in the WP2 (D2.3). We decided to replace them by the demonstration workflows, specifically designed for training and beginner users. During the second half of the project, the collection of demonstration workflows was extended with up to a total of 12 available workflows now, with 4 different flavours available for most of them: Jupyter Notebook, CWL, Pure Python, and Galaxy. All of them can be found in the BioBB website as well as in the special GitHub BioBB Workflows repository.</p>

[NEW] Objective D: Workflow prototype: Modelling and simulation of nucleic acids

Milestones	Status	Comment
<p><i>D1. Implement demonstration workflow as a Jupyter Notebook</i></p> <p><i>D2. Prepare the workflow to be used with PyCOMPSs and CWL</i></p> <p><i>D3. Make the workflow available through the GitHub repository and the BioExcel Cloud Portal</i></p> <p><i>D4. Implement and run the workflow in HPC infrastructure</i></p>	COMPLETED	<p>New workflows to model nucleic acids structures from sequence and extract DNA-specific flexibility parameters have been implemented and added to the collection of demonstration workflows. They are available in different flavours: Jupyter Notebook, CWL, Pure Python, and Galaxy, and can be found in the BioBB website as well as in the special GitHub BioBB Workflows repository.</p>

<i>(pre-exascale)</i>		
T2.3 Optimization of Workflows for Exascale computing		
Objective A: Workflows dynamicity, flexibility and elasticity		
Milestones	Status	Comment
<p><i>A1. Implement demonstration workflows showing dynamicity, flexibility, and elasticity</i></p> <p><i>A2. Make the workflow available through the GitHub repository and a BSC environment module</i></p>	COMPLETED	New PyCOMPSs runtime features that support fault tolerance at the task level and dynamic management of tasks exception are currently implemented in the pre-exascale workflows used for the HPC workflows presented in this document (section 4).
[New] Milestones	Status	Comment
<p><i>A3. Implement demonstration workflows showing resilience</i></p>	COMPLETED	The new PyCOMPSs checkpointing functionality has been tested. Thanks to the collaboration between the BioBB library and PyCOMPSs, the workflow manager is now compatible with the BioBB workflow “restart” property and is able to identify which tasks are already computed and which ones need to be executed.
Objective B: Singularity Workflows		
Milestones	Status	Comment
<p><i>B1. Implement demonstration workflows with Singularity containers</i></p> <p><i>B2. Make the workflow available through the GitHub repository and a BSC environment module</i></p>	COMPLETED	The pre-exascale use cases presented in the first half of the project (D2.2) contain workflows running Singularity containers (HADDOCK, pmx) in the BSC Marenostrum supercomputer and are controlled by the PyCOMPSs workflow manager. Workflows are available from the BioExcel GitHub repository.
[New] Milestones	Status	Comment
<p><i>B3. Install and run singularity workflows in different HPC infrastructures</i></p>	COMPLETED	The pre-exascale workflows running singularity containers were successfully exported to other European HPC centers. However, some tweaking had to be made in some of the cases, as direct singularity executions were not allowed (e.g. CEA Joliot-Curie, PCOCC system)
Objective C: Performance Analysis		
Milestones	Status	Comment
<p><i>C1. Analysis report of the performance of the workflows in different HPC systems</i></p>	COMPLETED	Performance analyses are regularly performed for the pre-exascale workflows running in the BSC MareNostrum supercomputer. PyCOMPSs traces are extracted from given runs and studied to further improve workflow efficiency. A couple of scalability studies have been performed with the BioExcel workflows in the second half of the project, one in BSC Marenostrum IV, Spain (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6283837) and one in the EuroHPC

		Discoverer supercomputer in Bulgaria (report in preparation).
Objective D: MolSSI collaboration		
Milestones	Status	Comment
<p>D1. Co-organize the second BioExcel-MolSSI workshop on workflows in biomolecular simulations (follow-up of the first workshop run in Barcelona in December 2018).</p> <p>D2. Continue with an active participation in the collaboration established, creating synergies between global biomolecular simulation workflow managers.</p>	COMPLETED	<p>The second BioExcel-MolSSI workshop on workflows in biomolecular simulations was organized and planned to be held from the 31 Mar, 2020 to the 02 Apr, 2020 in Washington DC, but was postponed until further notice due to COVID-19 travel concerns. The BioExcel-MolSSI collaboration is ongoing with the COVID-19 projects, especially with the COVID-19 Molecular Structure and Therapeutics Hub and the associated BioExcel COVID-19 database and web server.</p>
T2.4 Convergence of HPC and HPDA		
Objective A: Workflows integrating HPC and HPDA		
Milestones	Status	Comment
<p>A1. Implement demonstration workflows showing HPC/HPDA convergence</p> <p>A2. Make the workflow available through the GitHub repository and a BSC environment module</p>	PARTIALLY REDEFINED, PARTIALLY COMPLETED	<p>The task was partially redefined, and was finally divided in two projects:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Convergence of HPC and HPDA applied to MD simulations of COVID-19 related macromolecules, with the generation of a Big Data database of MD trajectories taken from the COVID-19 Molecular Structure and Therapeutics Hub. Workflows running meta-analysis on top of the whole database are in preparation. 2) Application of HPC resources on HPDA through the BSC Dislib library. Compilation of a benchmark for the PCA utility against popular tools in our field (MDtraj, MDAnalysis, ProDy, etc.), analysing both the differences in the resulting eigen values and eigen vectors, and the computational efficiency.
T2.5 Provisioning and maintaining a workflow environment		
Objective A: Infrastructure-as-Code description for Workflows		
Milestones	Status	Comment
<p>A1. Describe requirements for one existing workflow with Ansible</p> <p>A2. Integrate the workflow into BioExcel Portal</p>	NOT STARTED, BLOCKED, TO BE REPLACED WITH A4	<p>Documenting existing workflow installations from BioExcel-1 has proven problematic due to dependency on accurate documentation on both the original manual image creation process and the full image contents, which is not currently available. In light of the success of the new approaches to supporting workflows in dynamically generated VMs we suggest concentrating this effort primarily on generating and supporting new workflows/tutorials as reported in A3, and extended in A4.</p>

<i>A3. Create a new workflow or CWL training environment and integrate it into the portal</i>	COMPLETED	Two new recipes have been created: a dynamic VM with CWL and one with the Jupyter Notebook. Also, a more universal way of adding new workflows to the portal has been implemented, eliminating the need to hardcode new workflow types in the portal.
[New] Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>A4. Environments for workshop/training events</i>	COMPLETED	<p>The BinderHub proved to be the environment of choice for workshop/training events around BioBB. 2 events successfully used the “on-invitation” instance of the BioExcel BinderHub as the environment for hands-on exercises. Additionally, at the events where participants were supposed to complete exercises on their own computers, the open instance of BioExcel BinderHub was introduced to users as a fallback solution in case of problems with installation and for experimentation with other workflows.</p> <p>The only workshop that was initially planned to require VM-based environments for participants (CECAM Integrative approach to the theoretical study of chromatin) was rescheduled a couple of times due to the pandemic and finally is expected to use on-premises infrastructure instead of the BioExcel Portal.</p>
<i>A5. Other cloud providers than OpenStack for workflow environments</i>	INVESTIGATED, PARTIALLY COMPLETED	<p>Investigation of other cloud providers for both the VM-based environments and for the BinderHub was motivated by a number of factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● sustainability of the project after BioExcel 2 ● availability of the portal in case of EBI OpenStack outage (such as during migrations/upgrades) ● portability of the Portal solution. <p>For the VM-based environments, the investigation quickly concluded that due to security policies in the only OpenNebula installation available to WP2 (BSC), it will be impossible to reproduce the same model as in EBI Embassy and further investigation was suspended. The portability of the VM-based portal was also heavily exercised during the upgrade of the original OpenStack infrastructure in EBI, which proved that some components of the solution had implicit dependencies on the cloud provider and compatible software versions.</p> <p>For the BinderHub the attempt to install the BinderHub into OpenNebula has not been successful within the BioExcel 2 project timeframe, but no objective technical limitations of the infrastructure have been identified. The biggest blocker was the lack of a managed K8s cluster or K8s expertise within the team. Further attempts should be considered for BioExcel 3.</p> <p>Google GCP provided by EBI has been successfully used to support workflow environments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● secret store for BinderHub (KMS) ● PoC of Google authentication to BinderHub ● CWL-lab environment (VMs) as a backup solution

		<p>in case of BioExcel Portal outage (tested; not used in any event).</p> <p>The installation of BinderHub into GCP as an alternative to an unsuccessful OpenNebula attempt has been started and will be continued after BioExcel 2, possibly leading to a federated Binder PoC. It is expected to succeed based on positive experiences of other EBI teams outside BioExcel.</p>
Objective B: Shared Infrastructure for Workflows		
Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>B1. Investigate BinderHub and related technologies and try to install it/them locally on EBI infrastructure</i>	COMPLETED	The investigation and installation of the BinderHub were successful and the topic will be continued with new milestones being set up.
[New] Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>B2. Make the BinderHub installation production-ready</i>	COMPLETED	<p>Both instances of the BinderHub have been running in production. Live systems undergo constant improvements, but within the BioExcel 2 timeline, such goals were achieved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● gained expertise in K8s administration ● administration and deployment of multiple (including test) BinderHub environments via Helmsman ● logging infrastructure based on Fluentd and S3 ● basic monitoring
<i>B3. Integrate the BinderHub with the Portal</i>	COMPLETED	Binder entries in the BioExcel Portal have been marked with new icons and error handling has been improved.
<i>B4. Restrict access to the BinderHub by authentication/authorization</i>	INVESTIGATED, PARTIALLY COMPLETED	<p>Apart from the JWT authentication and authorisation allowing access for invited users only, Github authentication was introduced for the open access instance and authentication via multiple identity providers (GitHub and Google) not available by default in BinderHub was implemented and tested as a PoC.</p> <p>Restriction of access to selected repositories was successfully tried, but not switched on in the initial period in order to detect whether the open instance is used by malicious users.</p> <p>Logging out has still not been implemented completely (Binder session stays behind) in the BinderHub codebase and we have not managed to add it ourselves within BioExcel 2.</p>
<i>B5. Customise the BinderHub by adding BioExcel branding</i>	COMPLETED	The open BinderHub instance has received BioExcel branding and the UX was changed in comparison with mybinder.org as the users interact with the instance in a different way (they are not expected to bring their own repositories).

Objective C: Improved UX in BioExcel Portal		
Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>C1. Reimplement the portal so that sharing infrastructure and applications does not require the presence of a portal administrator during events</i>	COMPLETED	The concept of managers was introduced in the Portal, and thanks to it, the owner of the infrastructure can delegate granting access to the cloud to so called managers - typically organisers/trainers during the event. Additionally, more UX improvements around the training use-case were introduced, notably a way to log in to the Portal without the Elixir AAI account (which was previously reported as difficult/blocking by the users). The User Experience in the Portal is going to be continuously improved, but the work is going to be reported as a part of either objective A or B.
Objective D: Remote Environment for Jupyter Notebooks		
Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>D1. Investigate technologies involved. Try implementing ECP application that provides exclusive (VM) environment for Jupyter Notebook execution</i>	COMPLETED	We created the recipe for the dynamically built VM with Jupyter Notebook installation compatible with most of the demonstration workflows in D2.3 and we integrated it with the portal. We will continue the work looking into Docker requirements for workflows (New D2).
[New] Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>D2. Docker executions within Demonstration Workflows</i>	COMPLETED	Co-installation of the Docker Engine was introduced to the Jupyter VM application. No satisfactorily secure options of how to run workflows with Docker requirement in the BinderHub, resulting in Docker-in-Docker use case have been found.
Objective E: Platform for executing CWL-described workflows		
Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>E1. Obtain (possibly help to create) a CWL workflow in the BioExcel Community and run it in the GA4GH system; adapt the workflow to the system needs, if necessary</i>	PARTIALLY COMPLETED	We have successfully run a CWL workflow from the BioExcel Community [Github] on a demonstration installation of the Elixir Cloud & AAI distributed system. Elixir Cloud & AAI is one of the driver projects of the GA4GH initiative. We encountered problems related to the NFS storage used during the workflow run, which were already known to biobb implementers. On an installation backed by GlusterFS storage, the workflow ran successfully. After further evaluation, it is felt that further integration of the GA4GH/Elixir workflow system to the BioExcel portal and/or sharing access to the system with the BioExcel community is problematic at this time due to the immature status of the GA4GH system and its components. For this reason a watching brief will be kept on ongoing GA4GH developments and in the meantime milestone E1 is updated as below to explore additional/ alternative methods for executing CWL workflows. If the GA4GH system becomes sufficiently stable and mature at a later time to be offered directly to BioExcel users, its integration will be revisited. Within the BioExcel 2 timeline the GA4GH CWL workflow platform of the Elixir Cloud & AAI project has not gained

[Updated] Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>E1. Obtain (possibly help to create) a CWL workflow in the BioExcel Community and run it in the GA4GH system; adapt the workflow to the system needs, if necessary</i>	INVESTIGATED, PARTIALLY COMPLETED	<p>sufficient maturity to be offered to any users, including BioExcel community.</p> <p>Due to the lack of the general availability of the GA4GH system, alternative CWL workflow engines were tested. The objectives for those were set as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CWL 1.2 version support required by BioBB CWL workflows • support for private cloud environments such as OpenStack via either K8s support or an in-project provisioner for private cloud. <p>Such engines were tested with following unsatisfactory results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arvados K8s support is declared as working but not production ready. During the investigation blocking issues were discovered and reported back to Arvados developers. • ReaNa at the moment of testing had no support for CWL 1.2, but the support has since been added, so it might be reevaluated in the future. • Toil installation and initial runs of simpler BioBB workflows on K8s provided with OpenStack worked, however, Toil has a AWS API dependency even when installed on private cloud. This made further investigation impossible, when we ran out of Amazon credits. The removal of AWS API is planned by the Toil community, but the effort looks stalled. • cwl-tes has a very simple scheduling engine likely not satisfying biobb CWL needs, which in edge cases may mean that clustered execution might be less optimal than in a single node. During BioExcel 2, CWL 1.2 was still not supported; it is currently being added. • Toil with SLURM on private cloud without K8s use is still seen as a viable option and is currently under investigation within the Elixir community. Our team had insufficient SLURM installation and administration expertise to proceed with it.

T2.6 Retaining usability, interoperability, and reproducibility in Exascale workflows

Objective A: CWL task support in KNIME and Galaxy to enable scalable execution from graphical workflow managers

Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>A1. Demonstrate BioBB building blocks invoked from Galaxy as CWL tools</i>	PARTIALLY COMPLETED, REVISED	<p>We explored Galaxy's branch with experimental support for CWL tools in combination with Ansible-based install of Galaxy server. The conclusion is that installation of CWL tools in Galaxy servers is currently hard to automate, lacks documentation and still requires manual customization that needs further modifications of the building blocks.</p> <p>The BioBB building blocks was added to BSC's Galaxy Server https://biobb.usegalaxy.es/ directly as Python module,</p>

		which now seems more promising than waiting for Galaxy's CWL support to mature.
<i>A2. KNIME CWL node that executes containers remotely on multiple hosts</i>	INVESTIGATED, REVISED	<p>Following an initial investigation we decided not to pursue development of CWL support for KNIME, as we found its table-based data model worked poorly with the molecular dynamics data passed between BioExcel Building Blocks. Although this feature would be desirable, a reusable solution would also require far more effort than what is available for this sub-task, as it requires both dynamic Java GUI elements and integration with CWL execution backends.</p> <p>For a graphical workflow interface we will instead focus further on Galaxy (revised A1), which already supports multiple distributed backends like Slurm.</p> <p>We will make it easier to install a BioBB-enabled Galaxy instance (new A3), e.g. by industry users as we have already seen interest for (Diamond Light Source, WP3).</p> <p>For scalable CWL workflow execution we will instead focus on the workflow engine Toil, which can connect to Slurm, AWS and other backends (revised A2)</p>
[Updated/New] Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>A1. Demonstrate BioBB building blocks invoked from Galaxy as CWL tools</i>	PARTIALLY COMPLETED, REVISED	<p>The approach of installing BioBB as CWL tools in Galaxy was halted, as this feature is still deemed experimental by Galaxy developers, and we faced challenges for some complex data types that required custom Galaxy configuration, which made it difficult to complete the planned CWL vs native testing.</p> <p>However, the native BioBB blocks for Galaxy were tested on BSC's Galaxy server with successful rebuilding of BioBB workflows. These blocks should now be made generally available in Galaxy's Tool Shed for other Galaxy installations.</p> <p>We propose to combine these with our previous efforts to build an updated Ansible script for automated install of an BioBB-enabled Galaxy server (revised A3).</p>
<i>A2. BioExcel workflow running on multiple hosts on Toil</i>	PARTIALLY COMPLETED	<p>Toil has an ongoing dependency issue with AWS, for which a possible fix has been submitted, but the progress of this is unclear. As such we have not been able to test this backend.</p> <p>We have tested the COVID-19 BioExcel workflow on a range of HPC systems - using Toil with both SGE and Slurm job engines. As a result of these tests we have submitted several PR's for Toil, to ease the running of workflows across mixed serial and mpi queues. The flexibility of this approach is limited by local support job engine</p>

		configurations however, and more development of job engine support within Toil is needed to improve this situation. We are writing a report on running CWL/Toil workflows on HPC, which highlights where we think future development work is needed.
<i>A3. Improve automated installation of BioBB building blocks in Galaxy</i>	PARTIALLY COMPLETED	<p>Working with the SYNTHESYS+ project [16], we have customized the Galaxy project's Ansible scripts for automated setup of a Galaxy server to add tool installation, example workflow registration and user account activation.</p> <p>This effort is now being completed to a full BioBB tool/workflow install, to provide an automated setup of a complete BioBB-Galaxy instance.</p>
Objective B: HPC-specific annotations in CWL workflow to improve scheduling		
Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>B1. Extension of CWL engine using Singularity/SLURM-specific annotations</i>	PARTIALLY COMPLETED, REVISED	<p>While this approach was explored, CWL community agreement was not reached to make a generic solution.</p> <p>Specifying GPU support has been raised as more pressing by the community, particularly to optimize cloud allocation and scheduling. Collaborations have started with the CWL Leadership Team and NVIDIA developers.</p> <p>In particular Kubernetes is now showing promise as a mature backend for HW-specific workflow execution, e.g. using NVIDIA's gpu-feature-discovery labels.</p> <p>Instead of a generic approach we are now focusing on adding NVIDIA CUDA requirements as CWL annotations (revised B1), in order to use nvidia-docker (previously used successfully with GROMACS) along with informing Toil for selecting GPU/FPGA-accelerated AWS instances, also of importance in machine learning scenarios.</p>
<i>B2. Draft of generalized HPC annotation extension for CWL</i>	REVISED	<p>While we could not agree a generic annotation scheme for job managers, a specific NVIDIA CUDA annotation is now being formalized as a pragmatic extension for the CWL reference implementation.</p> <p>The goal is for this to further inform a generic vendor-neutral solution for the CWL specifications, e.g. recently released OpenCL 3.0 moved to almost all features being optional, and so a CWL workflow using GROMACS with OpenCL would need to specify which particular OpenCL features are desired or required.</p>
[Updated] Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>B1. Extension of CWL engine for GPU/Singularity/SLURM-specific scheduling</i>	PARTIALLY COMPLETED	This issue became urgent as on the UNIMAN HPC system, different queues have severely different waiting times. CWL execution in Toil was found to suffer in performance as it always used the same queue for any step, even when doing

		<p>small intermediate tasks in series.</p> <p>Work was done to improve this queue selection in Toil (see A2) and experimented with concatenating serial CWL steps into a single Slurm job. However conversations with Toil developers showed concatenation needs further work to consider fully the workflow semantics and Toil job state synchronisation.</p>
<i>B2. NVIDIA CUDA-specific CWL extension. Plan for generalized HPC annotation extension for CWL</i>	PARTIALLY COMPLETED	<p>Following lengthy discussions within the CWL community, considering the diversity of HW accelerators, an agreement was made to first develop this for NVIDIA CUDA.</p> <p>CUDA support was added to CWLtool by the CWL Community. This is now also supported by the Arvados engine. Future work therefore is to test the performance of CWL HPC workflows on cwltool and Arvados with GPU support.</p>

Objective C: Hardware-specific packaging of BioExcel-related tools in Conda / Docker

Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>C1. Demonstrate HW-optimized GROMACS in BioConda</i>	COMPLETED	<p>We enhanced our BioConda recipe for Gromacs to add multiple builds for memory sub-architectures as previously explored for container images, which was accepted by the BioConda community. We explored supporting Nvidia Cuda as BioConda dependencies, but found several interoperability issues. Conversations with NVIDIA staff confirm that it is preferable to inject CUDA libraries from the host rather than bundle them with the tool.</p> <p>Working with WP1 we explored heavily how to build and distribute hardware-dependent Docker/Singularity containers. Our previous method of a monolithic multi-build container was revised to use GitHub Actions and the Nvidia HPC Container Maker with alternate images for each architecture, that are then combined in a dispatcher container. This successful approach will be documented for the container/reproducibility community (new C3).</p>
<i>C2. Draft of Conda extension for hardware variant</i>	PARTIALLY COMPLETED	<p>Agreement was reached with BioConda community for convention for installing multiple binaries with a dispatcher on Conda environment load that modifies PATH. Further work includes writing up this methodology and investigate its applicability for other Conda packages (Revised C2).</p>
[Updated/New] Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>C2. Document Conda convention for building hardware variant binaries</i>	COMPLETED	<p>The process for building hardware variant binaries for the bioconda gromacs package has been documented. However, in 2022 we moved the gromacs conda package to conda-forge, and using their build system have also created a CUDA-enabled gromacs conda package. The documentation will be adapted and extended to reflect these changes. And we still need to test on another tool,</p>

		such as CP2K or machine learning libraries.
<i>C3. Document method for building hardware-specific Docker containers</i>	COMPLETED	Our approach for how to build containers of hardware-optimised binaries, using multiple-stages, GitHub Actions and dispatchers, has been documented in the blog posts gromacs-docker-hardware-specific-1 , gromacs-docker-hardware-specific-2 and gromacs-conda . These have been archived too , for long term preservation, and summarised in a UNIMAN Research IT post.

Objective D: Ensuring reproducible container execution on HPC

Milestones	Status	Comment
<i>D1. Demonstrate provenance recording of container image variant selection</i>	PARTIALLY COMPLETED	<p>Effort on CWL provenance capture was initially focused on provenance support in the Toil engine, as compared to the CWL reference implementation, Toil promised larger scale execution.</p> <p>In practice, however, we still found scalability and deployment issues with Toil on our HPC setups, and therefore focus moved back from detailed provenance capture to improving performance of Toil and our CWL workflows on HPC.</p> <p>Engagement with EOSC-Life, BY-COVID has helped define the provenance standards for Workflow Run Crate based on our earlier CWLProv work in BioExcel. An experimental cwlprov-to-crate is being developed by those projects, which we are testing on BioExcel CWL workflows. One nice side-effect of this is navigable HTML rendering of provenance for users.</p> <p>While this work captures container image, what is being developed further is lifting of tool definitions/identifiers so that the provenance also can record which BioBB and underlying tools were used [Soiland-Reyes 2022].</p>
<i>D2. Capturing GROMACS self-diagnostics as JSON provenance by BioBB/CWL to record hardware-dependent choices</i>	PARTIALLY COMPLETED	<p>The move to alternate images has reduced the need for recording this kind of self-diagnostic as provenance, however the need for reporting detailed dependency versions and compile settings remain.</p> <p>In practical tests across HPC systems, we found that it is not sufficient to record versions of the BioBB or gromacs alone, also dependencies such as fftw need to be installed in compatible versions. Therefore the whole Conda environment, with detailed version numbers, should be recorded and captured. A system of using conda-pack was established, primarily for bypassing HPC firewalls for software installation, but secondarily also for reproducible capture of dependencies.</p> <p>Now that hardware-optimised Conda distributions of GROMACS are completed, BioBB code can be updated to report the Conda environment as an additional output.</p>
[Updated/New] Milestones	Status	Comment

<p><i>D1. Demonstrate provenance recording of container image variant selection</i></p>	<p>INVESTIGATED</p>	<p>This milestone was initially to support partial provenance in order to improve performance. As noted in D3, CWL scalability was rather hampered even without provenance.</p> <p>The need for granular/partial provenance capture for CWLProv has been further discussed with the EOSC-Life/BY-COVID community for Workflow Run RO-Crate. Following requirements gathering from domain users it transpired that important provenance aspects are rather configuration settings, runtime environment, performance measurements, versioning and higher-level descriptions of workflows.</p> <p>This adds new requirements not just on the workflow engines but also the workflow steps (e.g. BioBB) in order to fully expose such details.</p>
<p><i>D2. Capture detailed version information from BioBB workflow provenance</i></p>	<p>REDEFINED</p>	<p>The disruption from COVID-19 meant reduced opportunities to establish wider tool community agreements (e.g. Biohackathons were largely virtual).</p> <p>We are redefining this milestone to focus solely on BioBB building blocks, which have more fine-grained control of their runtime environment. The new goal is to record provenance of the Conda environment with all dependencies for a given BioBB.</p>
<p><i>D3. Demonstrate scalable provenance recording of CWL workflows</i></p>	<p>STOPPED</p>	<p>As we ran into performance issues with CWL workflows on HPC even without provenance capture, focus was moved to improve CWL execution itself.</p> <p>Work has begun to capture benchmarking between different CWL engines on HPC systems, but as it's unlikely to be completed before the end of BioExcel-2, we have moved to writing up a whitepaper report on our performance experiences with CWL on HPC. The aim of the whitepaper is to provide a roadmap for future CWL developers.</p>

8 Conclusions

The ambitious and high risk goal proposed by the BioExcel partners back in 2015 for the development of a workflows library following a set of FAIR software development best practices has now produced a mature library, recognized by the European Commission as an *H2020 Innovation* that “addresses needs of existing markets” and is listed on the EU’s [Innovation Radar](#) platform. The result of years of development, shown in this deliverable, has confirmed that FAIR software development is not only possible, but powerful, useful, flexible, and in line with the new software requisites in science. A whole ecosystem has been created surrounding the library. REST-API programmatic access, a specific web-based GUI, Galaxy nodes, CWL specifications, and in summary, a broad variety of ways with which our users can start working with the library.

The interoperability given by the library design allows an easy interconnection of biomolecular tools. The uniform syntax considerably reduces the learning curve. With new tools being wrapped and new modules being added to the library, more complex and powerful workflows can be built. Workflows developed with the library are highly reproducible. The packaging system used is extremely helpful in installing the required dependencies, even working in HPC supercomputers, where the library in combination with PyCOMPSs workflow manager is showing its real power. Still, the methodology is not universal. Installation of the packages in old hardware or special architectures is sometimes failing (e.g. IBM Power9). Although not a problem for the library, binaries compiled and installed in the specific hardware are still recommended instead of the packaged ones. And, while it is nowadays quite common, not all tools are properly packaged in packages or containers.

The proposed WP2 roadmap, updated during the project, has not been completely fulfilled, but has been a good reference point, guiding the progress of the package. As expected, some of the milestones were redefined due to the pandemic, unpredictably opening new possibilities such as the BioExcel response capacity to adapt our pre-exascale workflows to COVID-19 research.

All in all, in spite of all the improvements achieved and the great features presented in this document, the library is having a slow uptake in the field. Using the developed methodology cannot be compared with the installation and execution of a new tool. It implies a complete change in philosophy, in the traditional way in which our community has built computational workflows for years and years. And this is only achievable with time and effort. The integration of BioExcel with standards and international initiatives is slowly helping our community getting familiar with the FAIR principles applied to software development. We believe that the work done in this work package has sowed the seeds of a revolution in the field, that will eventually see reproducible workflows as the right way to build, execute and share our scientific pipelines.

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